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CHILD RESCUE

Collective Awareness Platform for Missing Children Investigation and Rescue

D3.4 - ChildRescue Platform, APIs and Mobile App, Release II

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ChildRescue Project Profile

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Executive Summary

Deliverable D3.4 – “ChildRescue Platform, APIs and Mobile App Release II” constitutes the supporting documentation of the second and final iteration of the ChildRescue integrated platform (Release II). This report accompanies the delivered software up to M27 and provides a comprehensive view on the implemented functionalities of the second release of the ChildRescue platform and the mobile app, along with its technical verification.

The presentation of the integrated platform is divided between the core platform and the mobile application. The second platform release followed the integration plan described in D3.1 – “ChildRescue Architecture and Platform Design”, regarding foreseen functionalities and user roles. The changes and updates in comparison to the 1st release are highlighted in a dedicated section. A brief section for each of the implemented components follows, including a short description of each entity, its integration in the platform and some indicative screenshots. The required APIs for information retrieval and exchange are referenced inside the integration section of each component. Following is the presentation of the second release of the mobile application, with the relevant description and screenshots. For a complete reference of all implemented ChildRescue APIs for Release II, the last part of the platform presentation is dedicated to the API documentation.

The second thematic unit of this document pertains the ChildRescue technical verification and evaluation. The processes and criteria for verification of functional and non-functional requirements’ fulfilment and delivery of high-quality code have been defined during the 1st iteration in D3.3. Any changes to the initial framework are provided in this report. The second software release has been verified to comply with high-quality standards, and some of the results from completed tests are presented indicatively in this document.

The delivery of Release II signifies the completion of the third and final platform development iteration. This release features all foreseen components, functionalities and user roles. The second round of pilot activities in the context of WP4 – “Missing Persons Cases Piloting and Evaluation” to validate the platform in terms of added end-user value, will take place in M28, while a full public release is due for launching in M29. Needless to say, any feedback from the pilot activities and any technical oversights or failures will be addressed even if they arise after the end of WP3 and for the rest of the project’s duration.

Table of Contents

1	Introduction	10
2	ChildRescue Integrated Platform Release II	11
2.1	General Status and Changes from 1st Iteration	11
2.2	Core Platform and Components.....	12
2.2.1	Case Manager Component.....	13
2.2.1.1	<i>Changes from 1st Iteration.....</i>	<i>13</i>
2.2.1.2	<i>Description</i>	<i>13</i>
2.2.1.3	<i>Integration (may also include APIs).....</i>	<i>13</i>
2.2.1.4	<i>Updated Screenshots</i>	<i>14</i>
2.2.2	Control Room and Collaboration Space Components	16
2.2.2.1	<i>Changes from 1st Iteration.....</i>	<i>16</i>
2.2.2.2	<i>Description</i>	<i>16</i>
2.2.2.3	<i>Integration</i>	<i>17</i>
2.2.2.4	<i>Screenshots.....</i>	<i>17</i>
2.2.3	Privacy, Anonymisation, Synchronisation and Security Engine	18
2.2.3.1	<i>Changes from 1st Iteration.....</i>	<i>18</i>
2.2.3.2	<i>Description</i>	<i>18</i>
2.2.3.3	<i>Integration</i>	<i>18</i>
2.2.3.4	<i>Updated Screenshots</i>	<i>20</i>
2.2.4	Profiling and Prediction Engine.....	20
2.2.4.1	<i>Description</i>	<i>20</i>
2.2.4.2	<i>Integration</i>	<i>20</i>
2.2.4.3	<i>Screenshots.....</i>	<i>21</i>
2.2.5	Evaluation Engine	22
2.2.5.1	<i>Description</i>	<i>22</i>
2.2.5.2	<i>Integration</i>	<i>22</i>
2.2.5.3	<i>Screenshots.....</i>	<i>22</i>
2.2.6	Notification Engine	22
2.2.6.1	<i>Changes from 1st Iteration.....</i>	<i>22</i>
2.2.6.2	<i>Description</i>	<i>22</i>
2.2.6.3	<i>Integration</i>	<i>23</i>
2.2.6.4	<i>Screenshots.....</i>	<i>23</i>
2.2.7	Intelligent Search Engine.....	23
2.2.7.1	<i>Description</i>	<i>23</i>
2.2.7.2	<i>Integration</i>	<i>23</i>

2.2.7.3	<i>Screenshots</i>	23
2.2.8	Data Harmonisation and Interoperability Space.....	23
2.2.8.1	<i>Description</i>	23
2.2.8.2	<i>Integration</i>	23
2.2.8.3	<i>Screenshots</i>	24
2.2.9	Blockchain	24
2.2.9.1	<i>Description</i>	24
2.2.9.2	<i>Integration</i>	24
2.2.9.3	<i>Screenshots</i>	24
2.3	Mobile Application	24
2.3.1	Changes from 1 st Iteration	24
2.3.2	Description	25
2.3.3	Integration	26
2.3.4	Screenshots.....	29
2.3.4.1	<i>Welcome screen</i>	29
2.3.4.2	<i>Login-Register</i>	30
2.3.4.3	<i>Dashboard</i>	30
2.3.4.4	<i>Provide Information for specific alert</i>	31
2.3.4.5	<i>Provide Information</i>	32
2.3.4.6	<i>Case Management</i>	32
2.3.4.7	<i>Volunteers Collaboration Space</i>	33
2.4	APIs	34
2.4.1	Changes from 1 st Iteration	34
2.4.2	Mobile User Endpoints	35
2.4.2.1	<i>Mobile Alert Endpoints</i>	35
2.4.2.2	<i>Mobile Case Endpoints</i>	35
2.4.2.3	<i>Mobile Feedback Endpoints</i>	35
2.4.2.4	<i>Mobile User Endpoints</i>	36
2.4.2.5	<i>Other Endpoints</i>	36
2.4.3	Web User Endpoints.....	37
2.4.3.1	<i>Web Alert Endpoints</i>	37
2.4.3.2	<i>Web Case Endpoints</i>	37
2.4.3.3	<i>Web Facility Endpoints</i>	38
2.4.3.4	<i>Web Feedback Endpoints</i>	39
2.4.3.5	<i>Web Organisation Endpoints</i>	39
2.4.3.6	<i>Web User Endpoints</i>	40
2.4.3.7	<i>Other Endpoints</i>	40

2.4.4	Third party APIs.....	40
3	ChildRescue Integrated Platform Technical Verification and Evaluation	41
3.1	Technical Verification	41
3.1.1	Changes from 1 st Iteration	41
3.1.2	Integration Testing	41
3.1.2.1	<i>Approaches and Techniques</i>	<i>41</i>
3.1.3	Integration Points for ChildRescue Platform Release II	43
3.1.3.1	<i>User Registration</i>	<i>43</i>
3.1.3.2	<i>Receive information for specific case.....</i>	<i>43</i>
3.1.3.3	<i>Receive Alert</i>	<i>44</i>
3.1.3.4	<i>Send feedback for specific case</i>	<i>44</i>
3.1.3.5	<i>Send information for specific case.....</i>	<i>45</i>
3.1.4	Penetration Testing	45
3.1.4.1	<i>Types of Penetration Testing</i>	<i>46</i>
3.1.4.2	<i>Phases of Penetration Testing.....</i>	<i>46</i>
3.1.4.3	<i>Penetration Testing in ChildRescue</i>	<i>47</i>
3.1.5	Performance Testing	48
3.1.5.1	<i>Mobile Performance Testing.....</i>	<i>48</i>
3.1.5.2	<i>Backend Performance Testing.....</i>	<i>49</i>
3.2	Technical Evaluation	49
3.2.1	Changes from 1 st Iteration	49
3.2.2	Product Quality Model Categories.....	49
3.2.3	Technical KPIs of the ChildRescue Platform	51
4	Conclusions	56
	Annex I: Implemented User Stories Release II.....	57
	Annex II: Integration test tables.....	73
	Annex III: Performance test tables	86

List of Figures

Figure 2-1 Case Manager Main Page	14
Figure 2-2 Add New Case	14
Figure 2-3 Child Profile	15
Figure 2-4 Configure New Alert	15
Figure 2-5 Add New Fact	16
Figure 2-6 Control Room and Collaboration Space	17
Figure 2-7 Case Manager's Dashboard	17
Figure 2-8 Anonymisation Sequence Diagram	19
Figure 2-9 User Login	20
Figure 2-10 Places of Interest in "Places" tab under evaluation	21
Figure 2-11 Statistical Analysis overview	21
Figure 2-12 List of Facts with their Evaluations	22
Figure 2-13: ChildRescue Mobile App Technical Components	26
Figure 2-14: Mobile App Requests New Content	27
Figure 2-15: Mobile App Gets New Case Alert	28
Figure 2-16: Mobile app Receives New Notification	28
Figure 2-17: Welcome Title	29
Figure 2-18: Welcome Description	29
Figure 2-19: Login	30
Figure 2-20: Register Example	30
Figure 2-21: Dashboard - Registered User	31
Figure 2-22: Profile - Registered User	31
Figure 2-23: Provide Information-Complete Form (1/2)	31
Figure 2-24: Provide Information - Complete Form (2/2)	31
Figure 2-25: Provide Information Step 1	32
Figure 2-26: Provide Information Step 2	32
Figure 2-27: Provide Information	32
Figure 2-28: Dashboard	33
Figure 2-29: Case management	33
Figure 2-30: Collaboration spaces	34
Figure 2-31: Collaboration space - Provide feedback	34
Figure 2-32: Collaboration space - Timeline	34
Figure 3-1: User Registration Integration Point	43
Figure 3-2: Receive Information for Specific Case Integration Point	44
Figure 3-3 : Receive Alert Integration Point	44

Figure 3-4: Send Feedback Integration Point	45
Figure 3-5: Send Information for Specific Case Integration Point.....	45
Figure 3-6: Performance Simulation Scenario	49

List of Tables

Table 2-1 ChildRescue Platform technologies and frameworks	12
Table 2-2 Pseudonymisation and Anonymisation in ChildRescue.....	18
Table 2-3: ChildRescue Mobile App Versions	24
Table 2-4: ChildRescue Mobile App technologies and frameworks	26
Table 3-1: Product Quality Model Categories.....	50
Table 3-2: ChildRescue Technical Evaluation KPIs	51
Table II-1: User Registration Integration Test.....	73
Table II-2: Receive Information for Specific Case Integration Test	75
Table II-3: Receive Alert Integration Test.....	77
Table II-4: Send Feedback Integration Test.....	79
Table II-5: Send Information for Specific Case Integration Test	82

1 Introduction

D3.4 is released in the context of WP3 – “ChildRescue Platform Architecture Definition and Implementation” and contains the second and final complete integrated platform release, which is the result of the development and technical evaluation activities of tasks T3.2, T3.3 and T3.4 until [M27]. The deliverable is of type “Demonstrator”, meaning that it consists of the actual developed software and the relevant technical system report.

The present document consolidates elements from three types of technical documentation: 1. software architecture - the complete presentation of the core platform along with each implemented component, and the mobile application, 2. API documentation - the API calls and the corresponding components’ endpoints and 3. quality assurance documentation - technical platform verification and evaluation. Lastly, for the sake of completeness, implemented user stories are listed in Annex. As this is the 2nd iteration of deliverable D3.3 – “ChildRescue Platform, APIs and Mobile App Release I”, any changes from the 1st iteration are presented in the respective sections.

The main body of the document is structured as follows: the ChildRescue integrated platform is presented in Section 2, and the technical verification and evaluation results are outlined in Section 3. The deliverable gets its input from previous WP3 deliverables: D3.1, where the platform architecture, functionalities and relationships were designed and detailed based on elicited user requirements and developed user stories, D3.2 which contained the functional mock-ups for the web and mobile application user interfaces, D3.3 which was the 1st iteration of the integrated platform release. It is also aligned with D1.4 – “ChildRescue Integrated Methodology Release II”, where the final set of user stories was enlisted, and D2.5 – “Profiling Analytics and Privacy Methodological Foundations Release II” which reports the final analytics methodological approach implemented in the relevant ChildRescue components.

The current software release delivers all planned functionalities and addresses all user stories as refined in D1.4. User feedback and evaluation of the pilot phases will serve as a base for further minor updates and improvements in order to deliver high quality software that meets the users’ expectations. After the completion of the second piloting phase and the subsequent software improvements, the ChildRescue platform will be publicly released and will operate in ‘real-life’ cases and conditions.

2 ChildRescue Integrated Platform Release II

2.1 General Status and Changes from 1st Iteration

The current deliverable constitutes the second and final official software release of the ChildRescue platform, which is delivered together with this accompanying report. With regards to the 1st iteration in the context of D3.3 – “ChildRescue Platform, APIs and Mobile App Release I”, the current deliverable incorporates all components of the ChildRescue architecture and provides the full set of foreseen ChildRescue functionalities. This means that functionalities not supported in the first iteration are included and described in this release. At the same time, components developed in the first release have been further refined and developed, and their current status is presented in the respective sections.

The initial high-level architecture of the ChildRescue platform presented in D3.1 – “ChildRescue Architecture and Platform Design”, has been updated in the context of D3.3 in order to depict a number of modifications that occurred during the development activities and following discussions with pilot organisations. There are no further updates in the high-level architecture and comprising components to be reported in this iteration.

The general status of ChildRescue Platform and Mobile Release II can be summarised as follows: The integrated platform consists of two fully functional mobile applications (for the general public and registered organisation volunteers respectively) and the web application available to organisation users. The relevant code is stored into several private (for the time being, and until public release) repositories in GitHub and GitLab for better control and error handling:

1. Backend & APIs: <https://github.com/singularlogic/child-rescue>
2. Frontend & UI: <https://github.com/singularlogic/child-rescue-ui>
3. Mobile App Community ed.: <https://gitlab.com/childrescue/childrescue-community-android>
4. Mobile App for Volunteers ed.: <https://gitlab.com/childrescue/childrescue-volunteer-android>

A demo platform is setup on a private server with access rights available on request for security reasons. The mobile apps can be currently deployed as an .apk file, while they are also available as private apps (alpha testing mode) through the Google App store. The ChildRescue consortium has access to both for evaluation purposes. The second pilot operation will take place in [M28] as planned in D4.4 – “ChildRescue Pilot Handbook, Release II”, wherein the ChildRescue Release II will be further tested and evaluated in terms of functionality, user-friendliness and reliability. After performing any fixes and improvements that arose during the second pilot operation, the integrated platform will be in a state to support real users and will be publicly released. This is estimated to occur on [M29].

ChildRescue Platform Release II provides the following functionalities, always with regards to role-based user authorization: registration of organisation and members, creation and management of facilities (hosting and non-hosting), registration of volunteers and rescue teams, creation and management of children profiles, reception of evidence from mobile app users, notification generation and diffusion, case analytics, integration of 3rd party APIs from event aggregators to extract popular venues in an area, performance of behaviour and predictive analytics for the inference of possible points of interest (POIs), evidence evaluation with analytics and manual adjustment, intelligent search among existing profiles, team coordination and collaboration support, information credibility with the

integration of blockchain technology and enhanced security with the incorporation of the pseudonymisation/anonymisation component.

Furthermore, all user roles have been implemented, with their different access rights. Namely, the user roles supported in ChildRescue are: Organisation Owner (OO), Organisation Coordinator (OC), Case Manager (CM), Hosting Facility Manager (HFM), Network Manager (NM), Volunteer/Search and Rescue Team Member (RT), Simple User (SU), and Visitor (VU).

2.2 Core Platform and Components

The progress made until [M27] regarding the core platform development and its components is in line with the integration plan of D3.1. The ChildRescue Platform Release I and the available software infrastructure were the basis for the development activities that followed. The integration plan towards the second platform release included the expansion of the case and organisation management functionalities, the implementation and integration of the Collaboration Space for the search and rescue operation support, the integration of the various analytics processes. The completion of all web application user roles was also foreseen for this release.

The currently utilised technologies and frameworks are summarised in Table 2-1.

Table 2-1 ChildRescue Platform technologies and frameworks

Component	Implemented Framework
Backend	Python 3.6, Django framework ¹ , version 2.x
Frontend-UI	Vue.js ² , version 2.x
Database	PostgreSQL ³ , version 10.0
Notification Engine	Firebase Cloud Messaging ⁴ (server app)
REST API	Django Rest framework ⁵
Blockchain	Ethereum open-source platform

In the following sections, all ChildRescue components are presented individually: firstly, there is a brief description of the component's functionality, then the integration process and API calls are listed and lastly some indicative screenshots are presented. For components that were featured in D3.3 ("Case Manager", "Control Room", "Privacy", "Anonymisation, Synchronisation and Security Engine",

¹ <https://www.djangoproject.com/>

² <https://vuejs.org/>

³ <https://www.postgresql.org/>

⁴ <https://firebase.google.com/docs/cloud-messaging>

⁵ <https://www.django-rest-framework.org/>

"Notification Engine"), an additional subsection called "Changes from 1st iteration" is included, to highlight any updates from their first version.

2.2.1 Case Manager Component

2.2.1.1 Changes from 1st Iteration

The Case Manager component in the second release provides many additional functionalities in comparison to the first iteration. In Release II, the Case Manager combines the profile information available from the family and acquaintances of the child with the outputs of other components to compose the complete child profile. This additional information includes: POIs' evaluation, case classification and similar cases inferred by the "Profiling and Prediction Engine", a number of suggested places extracted from 3rd party APIs by the "Data Harmonisation and Interoperability Space", integration of information from the "Collaboration Space", the evaluation of the feedback performed by the "Evaluation Engine". The Case Manager component also provides the user interface for the "Intelligent Search Engine" functionality.

2.2.1.2 Description

The "Case Manager" component is the main component of ChildRescue and the main tool for the Case Manager, the Hosting Facility Manager and the Coordinator. It has multiple tasks and views attached to it. Through the Case Manager component, the web users can create and manage multi-layer case profiles, alerts and feedback. The user can also join a Collaboration Space for this case, add files or view some case-related data analytics. In short, everything related to an open case is gathered and handled by this component.

The multi-layer profile information is divided in groups of personal, demographic, physical, medical, psychological, social media data and other basic case information; this information together with outputs from other components, as described in the previous section, compose the complete profile of the missing child or the unaccompanied migrant minor. This profile is updated throughout the case's lifetime. The user can also perform a smart search through the "Case Manager" interface, in order to retrieve already existing records with similar-sounding registered full names.

Feedback can be created and edited through this component. The manager can also proceed to a manual assessment of feedback coming from citizens and manually mark it as relevant, irrelevant or credible.

The "Case Manager" component is also employed when the manager wants to create an alert for the case. The manager can customize the alert's content (e.g. direct data retrieval from the amber alert system, manually add free-text, attach files), duration, location/radius. These alerts can be updated after creation and even be deactivated (where they cannot be edited any more).

Finally, the "Case Manager" component interfaces the "Control Room and Collaboration Space" for the specific case and a diagram representation of case-related statistical analysis.

2.2.1.3 Integration (may also include APIs)

The "Case Manager" component was integrated in the ChildRescue Core Platform by expanding the platform's user interface and connecting the engine to the backend. The module's frontend has been integrated using JavaScript and it is based on the built-in modules of Vue.js framework to communicate with a RESTful API.

Concerning the component’s API calls there are four endpoints that make API calls: cases, facilities, alerts and feedbacks (evidences). Moreover, there are five basic API calls that every endpoint can perform; list, create, read, update and delete that are self-explanatory. However, it should be mentioned that the user will only be able to perform the calls list, update and read for the accounts of an organisation that he has access to. Additionally, a manager of the ChildRescue platform cannot update or delete a facility of a different organisation. The other endpoints have to do with the permission a user has and as such can be read, listed, created, updated and deleted.

2.2.1.4 Updated Screenshots

Figure 2-1 Case Manager Main Page

Figure 2-2 Add New Case

Figure 2-3 Child Profile

Figure 2-4 Configure New Alert

Figure 2-5 Add New Fact

2.2.2 Control Room and Collaboration Space Components

2.2.2.1 Changes from 1st Iteration

The Collaboration Space component was not implemented during the 1st iteration, so it is a new entry to this list. The Control Room, on the other hand, was partially implemented showing bits of its functionality in an aggregated format in the dashboard page of each organisation. In the 2nd iteration, the full functionality of both components is revealed, as they share a common interface, labelled as 'Control' tab inside an active case.

2.2.2.2 Description

The functionalities of the Control Room are of great significance for the Organisation Coordinator, the Case Manager and the Network Manager, as from this point they can organise, monitor and coordinate the search and rescue operations and teams, having a clear view on a map of everything related to the investigation part of the case. The interactive map displays the alerts, facts, POIs and volunteers of the case with their current location, as well as any geospatial information derived from the dynamic processing of the data (e.g. suggested radius for search areas).

The Collaboration Space component is integrated into the same view in order to facilitate the communication between all parties involved. An announcement "wall", typical to most social platforms, serves as the main collaboration tool for the fast, top-down sharing of new information, directions, images or other files from the side of the organisation users to the operational teams in the field and back. A chronological order is followed along with different colouring for fast tagging of the user role and the type of the post.

Furthermore, an overview of aggregated statistics is available through the Control Room component to the dashboard page for each organisation, for a quick view of the latest updates regarding all active cases.

2.2.2.3 Integration

Both components were integrated in the ChildRescue Platform UI using the Vue.js framework and the Google Maps API. It retrieves geographical information regarding the places of interest, as well as the current location of the rescue teams, given they have allowed this feature in their mobile app.

2.2.2.4 Screenshots

Figure 2-6 Control Room and Collaboration Space

Figure 2-7 Case Manager's Dashboard

2.2.3 Privacy, Anonymisation, Synchronisation and Security Engine

2.2.3.1 Changes from 1st Iteration

In the first iteration, the main security mechanisms developed involved the secure and encrypted user authorisation. The anonymisation and data privacy mechanisms were implemented during the 2nd iteration and are documented in the present report.

2.2.3.2 Description

The "Privacy, Anonymisation, Synchronisation & Security Engine" is a tool used mainly for security purposes to ensure that no sensitive data are released nor stored unencrypted. Moreover, the component implements the pseudonymisation and anonymisation operations on the platform data.

2.2.3.3 Integration

2.2.3.3.1 User Authentication

The one-way user password credentials encryption is based on the idea to store the hash values of passwords instead of the actual passwords provided by the users. For this purpose, the way that is used to validate the user's credentials is to apply the hash function to the password submitted by the user and compare it with the stored value in the database. If the hashes match the user is authenticated.

- `login`: Used to *post* user's email and password to the platform to login and obtain the token to access all other requests and identify the user.
- `register`: Used to *create* new user by providing the name, email, role password and organisation
- `logout`: Used to revoke the token and block the access to the requests
- `me`: Used to *get* information (name, email, organisation, avatar) of the logged user

2.2.3.3.2 Anonymisation and Pseudonymisation

The ChildRescue database needs to be properly anonymised and/or pseudonymised to ensure the protection of private and sensitive information of the various data subjects. As mentioned in D2.5 the project implements pseudonymisation and anonymisation techniques in the following cases:

Table 2-2 Pseudonymisation and Anonymisation in ChildRescue

	Personal data in case data	Personal data in user account data
Pseudonymisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upon case archiving 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upon registration and storage
Anonymisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upon activation of the right to be forgotten 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upon withdrawal of the consent form and deletion of the user account

The classification of the various data subject attributes according to the level of sensitivity (e.g. personal identifiers, quasi-identifiers etc) has been documented in D2.5 in section 3.3. Additionally, the anonymising techniques and the establishment of sufficient metrics that denote the level of anonymisation and re-identification risks were also documented in D2.5.

The implementation of the above techniques is achieved in ChildRescue using the ARX framework⁶. ARX framework provides a GUI as well as APIs that allow the definition of the appropriate generalisation hierarchies and privacy models; methods for both the addition of an arbitrary number of privacy models and the configuration of the parameters of each privacy model are provided. For ChildRescue, k-level anonymity with a value of 5 has been chosen together with l-diversity with an l-value equal to 2. These however can be changed by accessing the appropriate APIs defined. APIs for the addition of extra privacy models as well as for the configuration of existing ones have been implemented.

Anonymisation occurs at regular intervals; at each interval a complete copy of the ChildRescue database is anonymised and is exported to the anonymised database copy. As the values of the various anonymisation metrics depend upon the global characteristics of the dataset, it is necessary to substitute the anonymised database with the new anonymised dataset at each interval. This process is configured via appropriate cron jobs. **Error! Reference source not found.** depicts the sequence diagram of the anonymisation process in ChildRescue.

Figure2-8 Anonymisation Sequence Diagram

⁶ <https://arx.deidentifier.org/development/framework/>

2.2.3.4 Updated Screenshots

Figure 2-9 User Login

2.2.4 Profiling and Prediction Engine

2.2.4.1 Description

The “Profiling and Prediction Engine” performs analytics-related tasks for the case profiling and the child’s possible route estimation. It is employed in missing children cases. More specifically, this component applies some of the most popular algorithms to infer the following case information: classify the case as one of the “missing type” categories that have been identified, estimate the probability of disappearance (for hosting facilities), associate the case with similar past cases, and perform an initial evaluation of provided POIs. With the use of custom algorithms, this component can also evaluate next POIs and provide a proposed alert area. Last but not least, it can provide useful statistics regarding the running investigation and diffusion of the alerts towards the public. The outputs of the Profiling and Prediction Engine are available to the user through the case’s profile.

2.2.4.2 Integration

The integration of the algorithms is based on the python language and involves the Scikit-learn library. The data manipulation and pre-processing is handled by the Pandas library. For better user experience and to alleviate the impact of misclassification, most of the various outcomes are transformed in a human understandable format. For instance, instead of showing just a scoring value of 1 or 0 when predicting the type of the missing child case, the output is the predicted class label along with the respective degree of probability.

2.2.4.3 Screenshots

Figure 2-10 Places of Interest in "Places" tab under evaluation

Figure 2-11 Statistical Analysis overview

2.2.5 Evaluation Engine

2.2.5.1 Description

The "Evaluation Engine" component is responsible for the analysis and evaluation of feedback received through the ChildRescue mobile application. The evaluation is performed with the use of data analytics and following the methodological approach described in D2.5 – "ChildRescue_D2.5-Profiling Analytics and Privacy Methodological Foundations Release II_v1.00". In brief, the evaluation process is the following: a comparison is performed between the time and distance indicated by the feedback to the timing and place the child was last seen, to extract a "feasibility" factor. As a next step, a user credibility factor is extracted from his/her historical behaviour and profile completeness. The third step is the application of a spam detection algorithm to extract a "non-spam" factor. The outcomes of these three steps are combined to reach a final percentile regarding the reliability of the feedback. The outcome of this process is appended to the feedback and made available to the user through the "Facts" tab of the child's profile.

2.2.5.2 Integration

The integration of the algorithms is based on the python language and involves the Scikit-learn library. The data manipulation and pre-processing is handled by the Pandas library. For better user experience, most of the various outcomes are transformed in a human understandable format. For instance, when a 'spam' message is detected in the feedback list, it is labelled as 'spam' instead of showing the scoring value of the algorithm.

2.2.5.3 Screenshots

Since this is a background service, there are no screenshots available. However, we include a screenshot of the "Facts" tab of the child's profile, which depicts the result of the evaluation engine (score) next to each received and registered feedback.

LAST UPDATE ↓	DESCRIPTION ↑	ADDRESS	DATE OF INCIDENT	MEDIA	SCORE	SOURCE	CHECKED BY	STATUS	ID
2020-03-24 14:39:14		Αιτωλίας wtf, Χαλάνδρι 15...	2020-01-22 14:22:54		0	Anonymous		Spam	99
2020-01-22 13:33:22		Αιτωλίας 9, Χαλάνδρι 152 ...	2020-01-22 13:32:41		0	Anonymous		Pending	97
2020-01-20 17:07:22		Αιτωλίας 9, Χαλάνδρι 152 ...	2020-01-20 17:06:29		0	Anonymous		Pending	87

Figure 2-12 List of Facts with their Evaluations

2.2.6 Notification Engine

2.2.6.1 Changes from 1st Iteration

No significant changes from the 1st iteration to be reported.

2.2.6.2 Description

This component materializes the messaging system of the platform and is responsible for the notifications' diffusion to mobile users. It is based on Google's Firebase SDK for server-side functionality.

When a new alert is created or when a case is closed, the engine sends the appropriate message to all registered mobile users. The client side of the Firebase checks, then, the mobile's location and selects whether the notification will be shown or not.

2.2.6.3 Integration

The "Notification Engine" component is integrated to the Django backend as a unified platform library for sending push notifications to mobile devices and browsers. The library comes with Django REST Framework support.

2.2.6.4 Screenshots

Since this is a background service, there are no screenshots available.

2.2.7 Intelligent Search Engine

2.2.7.1 Description

The "Intelligent Search Engine" component provides the functionality of retrieving existing records with similar-sounding registered full names. This functionality is crucial for operators handling unaccompanied migrant minors' cases, as it is quite common for European handlers to register the same name of children from Asian countries in different ways.

2.2.7.2 Integration

As described in D2.5, the Intelligent Search Engine leverages the Levenshtein distance to find names with similar pronunciation and bring forth the top relevant records. This component provides a user interface through the Case Management page.

2.2.7.3 Screenshots

Since this is a background service, there are no screenshots available.

2.2.8 Data Harmonisation and Interoperability Space

2.2.8.1 Description

The "Data Harmonisation and Interoperability Space" performs background operations related to the connection to external data sources, the ingestion of data from these sources, their processing and transformation to an appropriate data format for the ChildRescue Engines and finally their storage. Limitations set by GDPR to any automated data retrieval from open social media profiles of persons led to subsequent restrictions by the most popular social media, like Facebook. Therefore, social networks about events and venues are used as external data sources in ChildRescue, as they are out of the GDPR restrictions' scope. Through the Data Harmonisation and Interoperability Space we acquire in an automated way the most popular events happening in the area at the time of the child's disappearance, as well as popular venues, which leads to a number of possible destinations. These locations are forwarded to the case's "Profiling and Prediction Engine" as new POIs with the appropriate indicator showing the source of information and are also evaluated.

2.2.8.2 Integration

The integration involves the implementation of three connectors to a respective number of external APIs, namely the Eventful API, the Foursquare API and the Twitter API. Even if these social networks are different in nature, the information required by the ChildRescue is the same: a possible destination for the missing child in question. Therefore, besides the connection to the APIs, another step is

developed which extracts the relevant information from the data received and transforms it to the same format.

2.2.8.3 Screenshots

Since this is a background service, there are no screenshots available.

2.2.9 Blockchain

2.2.9.1 Description

This component is responsible for the storage of feedback information received through the mobile app to a blockchain ledger for enhanced integrity and reliability. The data to be stored in the blockchain is a hash of the feedback details (i.e. id, case id, location, timestamp and any text or image the user provided as feedback). No personal information is stored due to the inherent opposition of the General Data Protection Regulation's 'right to be forgotten', to the non-repudiation principle of the blockchain.

2.2.9.2 Integration

Blockchain is an electronic ledger that can be openly shared among public or private users and that creates an unchangeable record of transactions, each one time-stamped and linked to the previous one. The ChildRescue blockchain ledger is implemented in the Ethereum open-source platform and stores a true and verifiable record of each and every piece of feedback received by the ChildRescue platform via an external connection (i.e. mobile app).

The process involves the selection and preparation of data, their transformation into a serialized object using a hash function, and the commit to the respective block related to the specific case. If the need arises, the administrator can retrieve the associated block and compare its contents with those of the ChildRescue database. The purpose of this process is to ensure and protect the integrity of the crowd sourced information.

2.2.9.3 Screenshots

Since this is a background service, there are no screenshots available.

2.3 Mobile Application

2.3.1 Changes from 1st Iteration

The first version of the ChildRescue mobile app includes the android version of the mobile app for the visitors, the simple users and the volunteers. The final version includes all the extended functionalities of the mobile app in android and iOS for the visitors and the simple users and in android for the volunteers. More specifically, the relevant functionalities and versions of both versions are provided in the following table (Table 2-3).

Table 2-3: ChildRescue Mobile App Versions

Version	User Roles	Supported framework	Core functionalities
Version 1.0	Visitor	Android	-Receive case alerts -Provide feedback
	Simple user	Android	-Receive case alerts -Provide feedback

			-User profile -Follow case
	Volunteer	Android	-Receive case alerts -Provide feedback -User profile Follow case
Version 2.0 (final)	Visitor	Android, iOS	-Receive case alerts -Provide feedback
	Simple user	Android, iOS	-Receive case alerts -Provide feedback -User profile - Follow case
	Volunteer	Android	-Receive case alerts -Provide feedback -User profile -Follow case -Timeline -Map view -Collaboration spaces

2.3.2 Description

The ChildRescue Mobile App incorporates the key features of the ChildRescue platform which are needed for the support of the general public in the various operations of the platform. The end users of the mobile app are the visitors (unregistered users), simple users (registered users) and volunteers (certified volunteers of the participating organisations). The mobile application provides all the necessary functionalities in order to support: 1) exchange of information about active cases alerts between the organisations and the general public which includes sharing public information about an active case and receiving feedback, 2) rescue teams alerting and management which includes real time communication in chatrooms with the volunteers, 3) task management of volunteers, 4) the end user's account management, as well as other functionalities.

The ChildRescue Mobile App consists of the following technical components:

- **UI Creator:** Responsible for the dynamic creation of the user interface which is offered to the end user.
- **Data Handler:** Implements the core business logic of the Mobile app and it is responsible for the management of the requests to the Backend Server by calling the respective REST endpoint of the Backend API and the routing of the information in the Mobile app client.
- **Notifications Manager:** Responsible for the management of the various notifications (push notifications, alerts, notifications for messages etc.)

- **Geolocations Manager:** Responsible for the management of the geolocation services of the mobile app

Figure 2-13: ChildRescue Mobile App Technical Components

The relevant technologies and frameworks that are being implemented by the aforementioned components are presented in the table below:

Table 2-4: ChildRescue Mobile App technologies and frameworks

Component	Implemented Framework
UI Creator	Android 8.0 Oreo ⁷
Data Handler	Android 8.0 Oreo
Notifications Manager	Firebase Cloud Messaging ⁸ , Android 8.0 Oreo
Geolocations Manager	LocationManager ⁹ , Geocoder ¹⁰ , Android 8.0 Oreo

2.3.3 Integration

The following sequence diagrams show the integration of the technical components of the ChildRescue Mobile App as well as the integration of the ChildRescue Mobile App with the Backend Platform. The

⁷ <https://www.android.com/versions/oreo-8-0/>

⁸ <https://firebase.google.com/docs/cloud-messaging>

⁹ <https://developer.android.com/reference/android/location/LocationManager.html>

¹⁰ <https://developer.android.com/reference/android/location/Geocoder>

sequence diagrams show the sequence of interactions between the aforementioned components based on three generic representative scenarios of a) request for content that is initiated from the Mobile App to the Backend Server, b) request for new alerts and c) receiving of new notifications.

Figure 2-14: Mobile App Requests New Content

Figure 2-15: Mobile App Gets New Case Alert

Figure 2-16: Mobile app Receives New Notification

2.3.4 Screenshots

In the current section, a set of representative screenshots of the mobile app for the simple users is presented since most of the features of v1.0 are common with the unregistered users and the volunteers. A detailed presentation of the mobile app is provided in "D4.4 – Pilots Planning and Preparation, Release II", in "Annex I: End User's Handbook".

2.3.4.1 Welcome screen

Upon installation two welcome screens are available. The first one provides the title of the ChildRescue project and the second one a brief description on how the user could get involved with ChildRescue. The user can proceed with the app either by pressing the "SKIP" button in the first case, or by pressing "GOT IT" in the second case.

Figure 2-17: Welcome Title

Figure 2-18: Welcome Description

2.3.4.2 Login-Register

As soon as the user visits the welcome page, she is redirected to the login screen (Figure 2-19), where she can choose whether she will login/register into the app or not.

Figure 2-19: Login

Figure 2-20: Register Example

2.3.4.3 Dashboard

Once the user logs into the mobile app, she is provided with the main dashboard (Figure 2-21). The user is also able to access the details of her account.

Figure 2-21: Dashboard - Registered User

Figure 2-22: Profile - Registered User

2.3.4.4 *Provide Information for specific alert*

The user is able to provide feedback about a specific case by clicking on the alert card of the specific case on her dashboard (Figure 2-23).

Figure 2-23: Provide Information - Complete Form (1/2)

Figure 2-24: Provide Information - Complete Form (2/2)

2.3.4.5 Provide Information

Besides the general information that is available through the dashboard view, the user can provide information on her own, in case she wants to provide feedback related to a missing child case. To do so, she is redirected to the respective view (Figure 2-25) by pressing the “info” icon from the top bar as shown up in Figure 2-21.

Figure 2-25: Provide Information Step 1

Figure 2-26: Provide Information Step 2

Figure 2-27: Provide Information

2.3.4.6 Case Management

Once the user logs into the mobile app, the main dashboard (Figure 2-28) is displayed. As can be observed there are two additional card items in the “CHILDRESCUE INFO” section. One of them is the “Cases” card item, which represents the open cases for which a volunteer has received an invitation to actively participate in. In other words, and as depicted Figure 2-29, in the tab “JOIN REQUEST” the list of cases for which an invitation has been sent to the volunteer is displayed. Apart from that, another list (“JOINED CASES”) with the accepted requests is also provided, and it represents all these cases for which the volunteer is an active member and contributes to. Finally, for the “JOINED Cases” the user’s location can be sent to the Network Manager at any time.

Figure 2-28: Dashboard

Figure 2-29: Case management

2.3.4.7 *Volunteers Collaboration Space*

In the current section the collaboration space is presented. More specifically, the cases that constitute the collaboration space are those that have already been joined from the volunteers (Figure 2-30). Consequently, the user has two options in terms of navigation.

The first option would be to send information to the Network Manager directly, by clicking the info icon at the top left corner of the card. This action will redirect the user to the respective form (Figure 2-31). Finally, the user fills out the form with the relevant information and presses the "SUBMIT INFORMATION" button in order to submit her feedback.

The second option is to check the overall feedback that has been sent by the Network Manager in respect of the specific case. For this purpose, a view that includes both a map and a timeline with specific case information is provided (Figure 2-32). From the same view, the user can also receive information related to the active members of a case and the feedback that has sent to the Network Manager by "MEMBERS" and "FEED" tab accordingly.

Figure 2-30: Collaboration spaces

Figure 2-31: Collaboration space - Provide feedback

Figure 2-32: Collaboration space - Timeline

2.4 APIs

2.4.1 Changes from 1st Iteration

The API Documentation presents the endpoints that are used in order to retrieve information for web and mobile users. During the 2nd iteration, several new endpoints were introduced, the most important of which are presented here, along with the ones from the 1st iteration.

The section is divided into three parts, the mobile and the web endpoints, based on the application that sends the request and a section for the APIs to third parties.

2.4.2 Mobile User Endpoints

2.4.2.1 Mobile Alert Endpoints

GET	/mobile/api/v1/alerts/
GET	/mobile/api/v1/alerts/{format}
GET	/mobile/api/v1/alerts/{id}/
GET	/mobile/api/v1/alerts/{id}{format}

A mobile user has access to retrieve alerts based on chronological and geographical criteria.

2.4.2.2 Mobile Case Endpoints

GET	/mobile/api/v1/cases/
GET	/mobile/api/v1/cases/{format}
GET	/mobile/api/v1/cases/{id}/
POST	/mobile/api/v1/cases/{id}/follow_case/
POST	/mobile/api/v1/cases/{id}/follow_case{format}
POST	/mobile/api/v1/cases/{id}/unfollow_case/
POST	/mobile/api/v1/cases/{id}/unfollow_case{format}
GET	/mobile/api/v1/cases/{id}{format}

A mobile user can retrieve cases and choose to follow or unfollow a case he is interested in knowing more in the future.

2.4.2.3 Mobile Feedback Endpoints

GET	/mobile/api/v1/feedbacks/
POST	/mobile/api/v1/feedbacks/
GET	/mobile/api/v1/feedbacks/{format}
POST	/mobile/api/v1/feedbacks/{format}
GET	/mobile/api/v1/feedbacks/{id}/
GET	/mobile/api/v1/feedbacks/{id}{format}

Using the mobile feedback endpoints, the user has the ability to send a feedback as well as read a feedback he has sent in the past.

2.4.2.4 Mobile User Endpoints

POST	/mobile/api/v1/users/forgot-password/
POST	/mobile/api/v1/users/forgot-password{format}
POST	/mobile/api/v1/users/login/
POST	/mobile/api/v1/users/login{format}
POST	/mobile/api/v1/users/logout/
POST	/mobile/api/v1/users/logout{format}
GET	/mobile/api/v1/users/me/
PUT	/mobile/api/v1/users/me/
PATCH	/mobile/api/v1/users/me/
DELETE	/mobile/api/v1/users/me/
GET	/mobile/api/v1/users/me{format}
PUT	/mobile/api/v1/users/me{format}
PATCH	/mobile/api/v1/users/me{format}
DELETE	/mobile/api/v1/users/me{format}
POST	/mobile/api/v1/users/register/
POST	/mobile/api/v1/users/register{format}
POST	/mobile/api/v1/users/reset-password/
POST	/mobile/api/v1/users/reset-password{format}

The mobile user endpoints are necessary in order to perform crucial functionalities for privacy and security purposes.

2.4.2.5 Other Endpoints

Other endpoints include the functionalities required by the volunteer app, like accepting an invitation to participate in a rescue team, the receiving of announcements and the posting of relevant feedback in the form of text or image.

2.4.3 Web User Endpoints

2.4.3.1 Web Alert Endpoints

GET	/web_admin/api/v1/alerts/
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/alerts/
GET	/web_admin/api/v1/alerts/{format}
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/alerts/{format}
GET	/web_admin/api/v1/alerts/{id}/
PUT	/web_admin/api/v1/alerts/{id}/
PATCH	/web_admin/api/v1/alerts/{id}/
DELETE	/web_admin/api/v1/alerts/{id}/
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/alerts/{id}/deactivate/
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/alerts/{id}/deactivate{format}
GET	/web_admin/api/v1/alerts/{id}{format}
PUT	/web_admin/api/v1/alerts/{id}{format}
PATCH	/web_admin/api/v1/alerts/{id}{format}
DELETE	/web_admin/api/v1/alerts/{id}{format}

The web alert endpoints are used to manage alerts, as well as deactivating an active alert.

2.4.3.2 Web Case Endpoints

GET	/web_admin/api/v1/cases/
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/cases/
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/cases/upload_image/
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/cases/upload_image{format}
GET	/web_admin/api/v1/cases/{format}
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/cases/{format}
GET	/web_admin/api/v1/cases/{id}/
PUT	/web_admin/api/v1/cases/{id}/
PATCH	/web_admin/api/v1/cases/{id}/
DELETE	/web_admin/api/v1/cases/{id}/
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/cases/{id}/archive_case/
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/cases/{id}/archive_case{format}
GET	/web_admin/api/v1/cases/{id}/close_case/
GET	/web_admin/api/v1/cases/{id}/close_case{format}
GET	/web_admin/api/v1/cases/{id}{format}
PUT	/web_admin/api/v1/cases/{id}{format}
PATCH	/web_admin/api/v1/cases/{id}{format}
DELETE	/web_admin/api/v1/cases/{id}{format}

One of the most commonly used entity in the web application is the case functionalities. They are used to get, edit, delete, archive or close a case and to upload files regarding a case.

2.4.3.3 Web Facility Endpoints

GET	/web_admin/api/v1/facilities/
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/facilities/
GET	/web_admin/api/v1/facilities/{format}
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/facilities/{format}
GET	/web_admin/api/v1/facilities/{id}/
PUT	/web_admin/api/v1/facilities/{id}/
PATCH	/web_admin/api/v1/facilities/{id}/
DELETE	/web_admin/api/v1/facilities/{id}/
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/facilities/{id}/add_child_in_facility/
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/facilities/{id}/add_child_in_facility{format}
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/facilities/{id}/completeness/
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/facilities/{id}/completeness{format}
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/facilities/{id}/facility_assign_hfm/
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/facilities/{id}/facility_assign_hfm{format}
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/facilities/{id}/remove_child_from_facility/
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/facilities/{id}/remove_child_from_facility{format}
GET	/web_admin/api/v1/facilities/{id}{format}
PUT	/web_admin/api/v1/facilities/{id}{format}
PATCH	/web_admin/api/v1/facilities/{id}{format}
DELETE	/web_admin/api/v1/facilities/{id}{format}

The endpoints above describe the functionalities of a facility. In addition, we are able to signify the presence (or not) of minors under a hosting facility.

2.4.3.4 Web Feedback Endpoints

GET	/web_admin/api/v1/feedbacks/
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/feedbacks/
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/feedbacks/upload_image/
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/feedbacks/upload_image{format}
GET	/web_admin/api/v1/feedbacks/{format}
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/feedbacks/{format}
GET	/web_admin/api/v1/feedbacks/{id}/
PUT	/web_admin/api/v1/feedbacks/{id}/
PATCH	/web_admin/api/v1/feedbacks/{id}/
GET	/web_admin/api/v1/feedbacks/{id}{format}
PUT	/web_admin/api/v1/feedbacks/{id}{format}
PATCH	/web_admin/api/v1/feedbacks/{id}{format}

The web feedback endpoints give the ability to the user to upload an image of an evidence, as part of the rest feedback information.

2.4.3.5 Web Organisation Endpoints

POST	/web_admin/api/v1/organizations/
GET	/web_admin/api/v1/organizations/{format}
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/organizations/{format}
GET	/web_admin/api/v1/organizations/{id}/
PUT	/web_admin/api/v1/organizations/{id}/
PATCH	/web_admin/api/v1/organizations/{id}/
DELETE	/web_admin/api/v1/organizations/{id}/
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/organizations/{id}/completeness/
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/organizations/{id}/completeness{format}
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/organizations/{id}/get_users/
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/organizations/{id}/get_users{format}
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/organizations/{id}/remove_user_from_organization/
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/organizations/{id}/remove_user_from_organization{format}
GET	/web_admin/api/v1/organizations/{id}{format}
PUT	/web_admin/api/v1/organizations/{id}{format}
PATCH	/web_admin/api/v1/organizations/{id}{format}
DELETE	/web_admin/api/v1/organizations/{id}{format}

Using the Organisation endpoints above, apart from the basic API calls (list, create, read, update, delete) we are able to get the number of occupants living in the facilities of an organisation as well as removing a user from the organisation.

2.4.3.6 Web User Endpoints

GET	/web_admin/api/v1/users/
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/users/forgot-password/
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/users/forgot-password{format}
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/users/login/
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/users/login{format}
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/users/logout/
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/users/logout{format}
GET	/web_admin/api/v1/users/me/
PUT	/web_admin/api/v1/users/me/
PATCH	/web_admin/api/v1/users/me/
DELETE	/web_admin/api/v1/users/me/
GET	/web_admin/api/v1/users/me{format}
PUT	/web_admin/api/v1/users/me{format}
PATCH	/web_admin/api/v1/users/me{format}
DELETE	/web_admin/api/v1/users/me{format}
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/users/register/
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/users/register{format}
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/users/reset-password/
POST	/web_admin/api/v1/users/reset-password{format}
GET	/web_admin/api/v1/users/{format}

Using the web user endpoints, we perform actions to authenticate a user or register a new account.

2.4.3.7 Other Endpoints

Other endpoints include the functionalities required by the control and collaboration space environment, like the management of announcements, the setting up of rescue teams and the designation of search areas. Additionally, a number of endpoints is dedicated to the results of the data analytics and the evaluation of profiles, feedback and POIs.

2.4.4 Third party APIs

- Foursquare API

GET <https://api.foursquare.com/v2/venues/trending>

- Eventful API

<http://eventful.com/events?l=areaname&within=10&units=km>

- Twitter Standard Search API

<https://api.twitter.com/1.1/search/tweets.json>

- Google Maps API

<https://maps.googleapis.com/maps/api/js>

- Open Street Map API (considered as alternative to Google Maps API)

<https://api06.dev.openstreetmap.org>

3 ChildRescue Integrated Platform Technical Verification and Evaluation

3.1 Technical Verification

A number of software projects rely solely on manual acceptance testing to verify that a piece of software conforms to its functional and non-functional requirements. Even where automated tests exist, they are often poorly maintained and out-of-date and thus require extensive manual testing. Testing is a cross-functional activity that involves the whole team and should be done continuously from the beginning of the project. Building qualitative software implies the creation of automated tests at multiple levels (e.g. unit, integration and acceptance) and running them as part of the deployment pipeline which is triggered every time a change is made to the application, its configuration or the environment and software stack that it runs on. Manual testing is also an essential part of building quality in showcases, usability testing, and exploratory testing that need to be done continuously throughout the project. For the testing of the ChildRescue platform both automated and manual testing have been adopted in order to combine testing reliability of automated testing tools and also allow for human observation, which may be more useful if the goal is user-friendliness.

The current section presents the results of the testing of the ChildRescue platform which includes the testing results between the various integration points of the ChildRescue platform which assure the valid end-to-end operation of the platform.

3.1.1 Changes from 1st Iteration

The current version provides the technical verification of the platform including the **updated** results of the unit and integration testing, as well as, the **new** results of the penetration testing and performance testing of the ChildRescue Platform (provided in sections 3.1.4 and 3.1.5).

3.1.2 Integration Testing

Integration testing is the phase in software testing in which individual software modules are combined and tested as a group.

3.1.2.1 *Approaches and Techniques*

Integration testing is the extension of unit testing. The main idea of integration testing is to start from two units that have already been tested (and combined into a component) to test the interface between them. A component, in this sense, refers to an integrated aggregation of more than one unit. In a realistic scenario, many units are combined into components, which are in turn aggregated into even larger parts of the program. The idea is to test combinations of pieces and eventually expand the process to test the modules with those of other groups. Eventually all the modules making up a process are tested together. Beyond that, if the program is composed of more than one process, they should be tested too.

Integration testing identifies problems that occur when units are combined. By using a test plan that requires testing each unit and ensures the viability of each before combining units, any errors discovered when combining units are likely related to the interface between them. This method reduces the number of possibilities to a far simpler level of analysis.

A system expert can perform integration testing in a variety of ways but the following are three most common strategies:

- The top-down approach of integration testing requires the highest-level modules to be tested and integrated first. This allows high-level logic and data flow to be tested early in the process and it tends to minimize the need for drivers. However, the need for stubs complicates test management and low-level utilities are tested relatively late in the development cycle. Another disadvantage of top-down integration testing is its poor support for early release of limited functionality.
- The bottom-up approach requires the lowest-level units to be tested and integrated first. These units are frequently referred to as utility modules. By using this approach, utility modules are tested early in the development process and the need for stubs is minimized. The downside, however, is that the need for drivers complicates test management and high-level logic and data flow are tested late. Like the top-down approach, the bottom-up approach also provides poor support for early release of limited functionality.
- The third approach, sometimes referred to as the “umbrella” approach, requires testing along functional data and control-flow paths. First, the inputs for functions are integrated in the bottom-up pattern discussed above. The outputs for each function are then integrated in the top-down manner. The primary advantage of this approach is the degree of support for early release of limited functionality. It also helps minimize the need for stubs and drivers. The potential weaknesses of this approach are significant, however, in that it can be less systematic than the other two approaches, leading to the need for more regression testing.

The ChildRescue consortium chose the last option, being the best, as it combines the best of both worlds. It allows all participating entities, to execute simultaneously multiple testing in several components. Integration testing plays a significant role for the proper functionality of the platform. As indicated by the system architecture in D3.1 and the first version of the integrated platform in D3.3, the ChildRescue Platform consists of a number of components implemented by different partners with different technologies addressing different functionalities. The valid integration of these components was a great need and integration testing became a priority at a very early stage of the development.

For testing the network communication of web services that were undergoing development we also employed service virtualisation techniques. In software engineering, service virtualisation is a method to emulate the behaviour of specific components in component-based applications. It is used to provide software development and testing teams access to dependent system components that are needed to exercise an application under test, but are unavailable or difficult-to-access for development and testing purposes. With the behaviour of the dependent components "virtualised" testing and development can proceed without accessing the actual live components, until they become available.

Service virtualisation involves creation and deployment of a "virtual asset" that simulates the behaviour of a real component which is required to exercise the application under test, but is difficult or impossible to access for development and testing purposes.

A virtual asset stands in for a dependent component by listening for requests and returning an appropriate response—with the appropriate performance. For example, in a web service, this involves listening for a RESTful message over HTTP and then returning another message. The virtual asset's functionality and performance tries to reflect the actual functionality of the component, also tries to simulate exceptional conditions (such as extreme loads or error conditions) to determine how the application under test responds under those circumstances.

Virtual assets are typically created either by providing logs representing historical communication among components, analysing service interface specifications (such as RESTful) or defining the behaviour manually with various interface controls and data source values. They are then further configured to represent specific data, functionality, and response times. After the release of a web service prototype, it substitutes the virtualised one, in order for the integrated testing of the real one to be initiated.

3.1.3 Integration Points for ChildRescue Platform Release II

In the following section we present a set of representative testing results of the integration between the backend platform and the UI as well as with the mobile app. For each integration point the relevant sequence diagram is provided, as well as the relevant integration test is provided in the *Annex II: Integration test tables*.

3.1.3.1 User Registration

The relevant integration steps and interactions for the user registration are shown in the sequence diagram below:

Figure 3-1: User Registration Integration Point

3.1.3.2 Receive information for specific case

The relevant integration steps and interactions for the available information that has been sent for a specific case are shown in the sequence diagram below:

Figure 3-2: Receive Information for Specific Case Integration Point

3.1.3.3 *Receive Alert*

The relevant integration steps and interactions for the available alerts are shown in the sequence diagram below:

Figure 3-3 : Receive Alert Integration Point

3.1.3.4 *Send feedback for specific case*

The relevant integration steps and interactions for the feedback provided by the user are shown in the sequence diagram below:

Figure 3-4: Send Feedback Integration Point

3.1.3.5 Send information for specific case

The relevant integration steps and interactions for the feed provided by the volunteer are shown in the sequence diagram below:

Figure 3-5: Send Information for Specific Case Integration Point

3.1.4 Penetration Testing

The Penetration Testing (“pen test” for short) is a type of Security Testing that uncovers vulnerabilities, threats, risks in a software application, network or web application that an attacker could exploit. The

purpose of a pen test is to find all the security vulnerabilities that are present in the system being tested.

3.1.4.1 *Types of Penetration Testing*

The type of penetration test selected usually depends on the scope and whether the organisation wants to simulate an attack by an employee, Network Admin (Internal Sources) or by External Sources. There are three types of Penetration Testing, namely: **a) Black Box Testing, b) White Box Penetration Testing, c) Grey Box Penetration Testing.**

In black-box penetration testing, a tester has no knowledge about the systems to be tested. He is responsible to collect information about the target network or system. In a white-box penetration testing, the tester is usually provided with complete information about the network or systems to be tested including the IP address schema, source code, OS details, etc. This can be considered as a simulation of an attack by any Internal sources (Employees of an Organization). In a grey box penetration testing, a tester is provided with partial knowledge of the system. It can be considered as an attack by an external hacker who had gained illegitimate access to an organization's network infrastructure documents.

3.1.4.2 *Phases of Penetration Testing*

A typical penetration testing includes the following steps:

Step 1) Planning phase

1. Scope & Strategy of the assignment is determined
2. Existing security policies, standards are used for defining the scope

Step 2) Discovery phase

1. Collect as much information as possible about the system including data in the system, usernames and even passwords. This is also called as **FINGERPRINTING**
2. Scan and Probe into the ports
3. Check for vulnerabilities of the system

Step 3) Attack phase

1. Find exploits for various vulnerabilities You need necessary security Privileges to exploit the system

Step 4) Reporting phase

1. A report must contain detailed findings
2. Risks of vulnerabilities found and their Impact on business
3. Recommendations and solutions, if any

The prime task in penetration testing is to gather system information. There are two ways to gather information -

- 'One to one' or 'one to many' model with respect to host: A tester performs techniques in a linear way against either one target host or a logical grouping of target hosts (e.g. a subnet).
- 'Many to one' or 'many to many' model: The tester utilises multiple hosts to execute information gathering techniques in a random, rate-limited, and in non-linear.

3.1.4.3 Penetration Testing in ChildRescue

The type of penetration testing that was chosen for ChildRescue was the Grey Box and it was implemented using the Burp tool¹¹, as well as, programmatically, using Python scripts at the ChildRescue web platform (<https://platform.childrescue.eu>) for all user roles. Most of the findings were already known and anticipated given the current stage of the implementation and no major vulnerability was identified. The detailed results of the penetration tests are not released as part of this publication for security reasons. A second wave of penetration tests is scheduled for when the results from the second pilot phase are in place.

The main security risks that were explored and tested for the ChildRescue platform are the following:

1. **Injection.** Injection flaws, such as SQL, NoSQL, OS, and LDAP injection, occur when untrusted data is sent to an interpreter as part of a command or query. The attacker's hostile data can trick the interpreter into executing unintended commands or accessing data without proper authorization.
2. **Broken Authentication.** Application functions related to authentication and session management are often implemented incorrectly, allowing attackers to compromise passwords, keys, or session tokens, or to exploit other implementation flaws to assume other users' identities temporarily or permanently.
3. **Sensitive Data Exposure.** Many web applications and APIs do not properly protect sensitive data and PII. Sensitive data may be compromised without extra protection, such as encryption at rest or in transit, and requires special precautions when exchanged with the browser.
4. **XML External Entities (XXE).** Many older or poorly configured XML processors evaluate external entity references within XML documents. External entities can be used to disclose internal files using the file URI handler, internal file shares, internal port scanning, remote code execution, and denial of service attacks.
5. **Broken Access Control.** Restrictions on what authenticated users are allowed to do are often not properly enforced. Attackers can exploit these flaws to access unauthorized functionality and/or data, such as access other users' accounts, view sensitive files, modify other users' data, change access rights, etc.
6. **Security Misconfiguration.** Security misconfiguration is the most commonly seen issue. This is commonly a result of insecure default configurations, incomplete or ad hoc configurations, open cloud storage, misconfigured HTTP headers, and verbose error messages containing sensitive information. Not only must all operating systems, frameworks, libraries, and applications be securely configured, but they must be patched/upgraded in a timely fashion.
7. **Cross-Site Scripting XSS.** XSS flaws occur whenever an application includes untrusted data in a new web page without proper validation or escaping, or updates an existing web page with user-supplied data using a browser API that can create HTML or JavaScript. XSS allows attackers to execute scripts in the victim's browser which can hijack user sessions, deface web sites, or redirect the user to malicious sites.

¹¹ <https://portswigger.net/burp/pro>

8. **Insecure Deserialization.** Insecure deserialization often leads to remote code execution. Even if deserialization flaws do not result in remote code execution, they can be used to perform attacks, including replay attacks, injection attacks, and privilege escalation attacks.
9. **Using Components with Known Vulnerabilities.** Components, such as libraries, frameworks, and other software modules, run with the same privileges as the application. If a vulnerable component is exploited, such an attack can facilitate serious data loss or server takeover. Applications and APIs using components with known vulnerabilities may undermine application defences and enable various attacks and impacts.
10. **Insufficient Logging & Monitoring.** Insufficient logging and monitoring, coupled with missing or ineffective integration with incident response, allows attackers to further attack systems, maintain persistence, pivot to more systems, and tamper, extract, or destroy data.

3.1.5 Performance Testing

3.1.5.1 Mobile Performance Testing

In the current section, the code performance testing for the mobile application is performed and presented, which evaluates the overall performance of the system. In this context, individual metrics in some representative endpoints along with a specific scenario are measured, and these results, represent the performance metrics of the mobile application. This performance testing process will ensure the proper performance behaviour of the application as a whole.

Due to the fact that the mobile application which is indented for volunteers is the one with the majority of features developed in the context of ChildRescue, the executed scenario, along with some representative endpoints are performed through this application. More specifically, in this section, a specific scenario was simulated to test the performance of the mobile application by configuring a mobile device, which was utilised for the test recording. Performance metrics were conducted using **Apache JMeter**¹², which records every action applying its own proxy. Due to this end, the internet connection was configured in a particular way, so that the network of the mobile device would use the JMeter proxy server. Moreover, in the frame of this implementation, the appropriate JMeter Certificate was stored in the mobile device as well. Once this configuration process was completed the scenario was executed.

In this scenario, a volunteer user performs a login in order for her to have access to the entire application. Right after a quick overview of the dashboard, the user visits the case management card in order to be aware of the open cases, in which she is an active member. Subsequently, the user decides to send some information to the Network manager concerning a specific case. Once the information has been sent via the relevant form, the user is redirected to the screen where all the information that she has received for this specific case so far is displayed. Finally, after checking these messages, the user decides to logout from the application.

In the context of the aforementioned scenario a Thread Group for simulating users was created. The number of simulated users was 10, with a Ramp Up Period, defining the time it takes for all the threads to start, equal to ten seconds. The results can be seen in Figure 3-6. Metrics such as the average, minimum and maximum response time were recorded. As can be seen from the results, the most time-

¹² <https://jmeter.apache.org/>

consuming process was Login, which required the authentication and the verification of the user. The average response time for the current version has been 189.57ms, in total of 1.385 requests, and the percentage of failed requests is zero.

Statistics												
Requests	Executions			Response Times (ms)						Throughput	Network (KB/sec)	
Label	#Samples	KO	Error %	Average	Min	Max	90th pct	95th pct	99th pct	Transactions/s	Received	Sent
Total	1385	0	0.00%	189.57	90	1082	305.40	421.80	867.56	22.98	45.06	7.07
Case Management	59	0	0.00%	185.54	99	418	239.00	266.00	418.00	1.04	0.32	0.30
Feedback	57	0	0.00%	713.04	521	1390	856.80	976.20	1390.00	1.03	1.61	1.85
Login	59	0	0.00%	1715.02	1335	2460	1874.00	1998.00	2460.00	1.01	4.22	2.93
Logout	53	0	0.00%	223.43	108	369	264.40	328.70	369.00	1.03	0.31	0.36
Scenario	53	0	0.00%	4583.17	3725	5228	5074.80	5142.10	5228.00	0.95	46.66	7.06

Figure 3-6: Performance Simulation Scenario

3.1.5.2 Backend Performance Testing

In the backend performance testing, each performed request and response related to the ChildRescue API is recorded, during the execution of the scenario. More specifically, a recording template was created, in order for the navigation to be recorded. During the navigation, several transactions were performed, and each one of them, represents a Transaction Controller. Each transaction controller consists of several HTTP requests, which will be presented in *Annex III: Performance test tables*, along with their sample results, which denote specific metrics for each one of these requests.

3.2 Technical Evaluation

For the technical evaluation of the ChildRescue platform, the "Product Quality Model" from ISO/IEC 25010:2011¹³ was used as a guidance for the generation of the technical Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) of the Platform. Each aspect of the model was examined on whether and how it covers the requirements of the project. Based on this analysis, a number of relevant KPIs were identified. Section 3.2.2 examines which of the Product Quality Model categories are relative to the project, while in section 3.2.3 the specific, project-related technical KPIs are described. This section describes solely the technical analysis, which took place at the latest cycle of the platform implementation.

3.2.1 Changes from 1st Iteration

The current version provides an updated list of the Product Quality Model sub-characteristics which are relevant to the ChildRescue platform, as well as the updated KPIs list.

3.2.2 Product Quality Model Categories

Table 3-1 showcases the sub-characteristics of each category of the Product Quality Model which are relevant to the ChildRescue platform.

¹³ <https://www.iso.org/standard/35733.html>

Table 3-1: Product Quality Model Categories

Sub-characteristics	Definition	Relation to ChildRescue
Functional suitability		
Completeness	Degree to which the set of functions covers all the specified tasks and user objectives.	YES
Correctness	System provides the correct results with the needed degree of precision.	YES
Appropriateness	The functions facilitate the accomplishment of specified tasks and objectives.	YES
Performance efficiency		
Time behaviour	Response, processing times and throughput rates of a system, when performing its functions, meet requirements.	YES
Resource utilisation	The amounts and types of resources used by a system, when performing its functions, meet requirements.	YES
Compatibility		
Co-existence	Product can perform its functions efficiently while sharing environment and resources with other products.	YES
Interoperability	A system can exchange information with other systems and use the information that has been exchanged.	YES
Usability		
Ease of Use	System has attributes that make it easy to operate and control.	YES
User error protection	System protects users against making errors.	YES
User interface aesthetics	User interface enables pleasing and satisfying interaction for the user.	YES
Technical Accessibility	System can be used by people with the widest range of characteristics and capabilities.	YES
Reliability		
Maturity	System meets needs for reliability under normal operation.	YES
Availability	System is operational and accessible when required for use.	YES
Fault tolerance	System operates as intended despite the presence of hardware or software faults.	YES
Security		
Confidentiality	System ensures that data is accessible only to those authorised to have access.	YES
Integrity	System prevents unauthorised access to, or modification of, computer programs or data.	YES
Non-repudiation	Actions or events can be proven to have taken place, so that the events or actions cannot be repudiated later.	YES

Authenticity	The identity of a subject or resource can be proved to be the one claimed.	YES
Maintainability		
Modularity	System is composed of components such that a change to one component has minimal impact on other components.	YES
Reusability	An asset can be used in more than one system, or in building other assets.	YES
Testability	Effectiveness and efficiency with which test criteria can be established for a system.	YES
Portability		
Installability	Effectiveness and efficiency with which a system can be successfully installed and/or uninstalled.	YES (only for mobile app)

To validate that the platform fulfils adequately all technical requirements, a set of technical methodologies and tools were used, and these include:

- W3C Mark-up Validation Service for HTML/XHTML and CSS validation in the context of technical quality assurance.
- Sonar for the integrated platform Quality Assurance
- Unit Testing on discrete platform components
- Integration testing on the integrated platform
- The CI/CD methodology and tools¹⁴ of the Gitlab platform are also used to support the mobile app development lifecycle

3.2.3 Technical KPIs of the ChildRescue Platform

Based on the tables presented in the previous sections that reveal which criteria could be measured during the ChildRescue operation, and based on the fact that the ISO/IEC 25010:2011 standard does not define specific attributes (measuring ways) for each one of the sub-characteristics, the following list of KPIs has been defined to allow the technical evaluation of the ChildRescue platform.

Table 3-2: ChildRescue Technical Evaluation KPIs

Sub-characteristics	KPIs	Calculation Type	Recommended Limit	Value	Mandatory/Optional	Comments
Functional suitability						
Functional completeness	Percentage of completed Use Cases / Usage Scenarios	(Completed Use Cases / Defined Use Cases) * 100 %	100%	100 %	M	Final version covers all use cases
Functional correctness	Percentage of Use Cases without	(Completed Use Cases without bugs / Defined	>90%	95%	M	Achieved for v1.0, the first pilot phase, and the final version. To be

¹⁴ <https://docs.gitlab.com/ee/ci/>

	reported bugs, after tests	Use Cases) * 100 %				further analysed during the execution of the second pilots.
Functional appropriateness	Percentage of tasks accomplished / Tasks Defined	(Accomplished Tasks / Tasks Defined) * 100%	>90%	100 %	M	Achieved for v1.0, the first pilot phase, and the final version. To be further analysed during the execution of the second pilots.
Performance efficiency						
Time behaviour	Average Latency	(Total Response Time)/(No. of Requests)	<= 1 sec	<1 sec.	M	All requests are executed in 0,5 -1 sec. A Performance test was implemented for final version which attests the results.
Resource utilisation	Mean % CPU Utilisation	(Σ (% CPU utilisation probes))/(No. of probes)	<60%	<12 %	M	No critical issues for final version. A Performance test was implemented for final version which attests the results.
	Mean Memory Usage	(Σ (RAM Megabytes used in each probe))/(No. of probes)	<60%	<27 %	M	No critical issues for final version. A Performance test was implemented for final version which attests the results.
Compatibility						
Co-existence	Ability to host in a single environment	Can the ChildRescue components operate in a shared environment? YES/NO	YES	YES	O	Virtualization and dockerization techniques are applied
Usability						
Ease of Use¹⁵	Number of clicks required	Number of clicks required to reach	<3	~1-2 clicks	M	

¹⁵ Behavioural characteristics are part of the quality in use model, here only metrics that can be automatically extracted are mentioned

	to reach requested information	required information				
User error protection	System crash on user errors	Does the whole crash on user errors? YES/NO	NO	NO	M	
User interface aesthetics	User Interface Accessibility standardisation	No. of User Interface Accessibility standards followed	1	1	M	
Technical Accessibility	Cross-Platform Accessibility	ChildRescue platform is accessible and operational through different platforms (e.g. Windows / MacOS / Linux)	YES	YES	M	The final version of the mobile app (for visitors and simple users) will be also available in iOS. The mobile app of the volunteers will be provided in android.
	Cross-Browser Accessibility	ChildRescue platform is accessible and operational through different browsers (e.g. Chrome / Firefox/EDGE)	YES	YES	M	Achieved for final version
	Cross-Device Accessibility	ChildRescue platform accessible and operational through different devices (e.g. PC / Laptop/ Tablet / Smartphone)	YES	YES	M	Achieved for final version
Maturity	Max. Concurrent Users Supported	No. of Max. Concurrent Users Recorded	>100 users	>100 users	M	Achieved in simulation through automated stress testing for final version
	Simultaneous Requests	No. of Simultaneous Requests (e.g. page open)	>75	>100	M	Achieved in simulation through automated stress testing for final version

Availability	% Monthly Availability	1- ((Downtown Time Minutes)/(Month Days*24*60))	>90%	>99%	M	Any downtime documented was intentional and only for infrastructure upgrade.
	Error Rate	(No. of Problematic Requests)/(Total Number of Requests)	<10%	~2%	M	No critical issues for final version
Fault tolerance	Number of Software problems identified without affecting the platform	No. of Non-Critical Software Errors	<10	3	M	No critical issues for final version
Security						
Confidentiality	Incidents of ownership changes and accessing prohibited information	No. of incidents recorded	0 (zero)	0	M	No critical issues for final version
Integrity	Incidents of authentication mechanism breaches	No. of incidents recorded	0 (zero)	0	M	No critical issues for final version
Authenticity	Level of User Authenticity	Can you identify whether a subject is the one it claims to be? YES/NO/Partially	YES	YES	M	Volunteers are certified organization members.
	Level of Data Resource Authenticity	Can you identify whether a resource is the one it claims to be? (or e.g. is it created by robots) YES/NO/Partially	YES	YES	O	Integration and exchange of information is encrypted and token protected.
Maintainability						
Modifiability	% of Update Effectiveness	(No. of updates preformed without noticing operational problems)/(No.	>75%	100%	M	All updates were performed smoothly for final version

Testability	Level of Testing	of updates performed) Are tests able to probe the ChildRescue platform behaviour? YES/NO/Partially	YES	YES	M	Unit, integration and acceptance tests are also supported for the technical testing of the platform.
Adaptability	Mean No. of Errors per Installation	Portability (No. of Total Errors recorded during Installations)/(Total No. of Installations)	<1	0	O	No installation errors were recorded for final version

4 Conclusions

The present document accompanies the code developed by the technical partners of the project and it is a descriptive guide about all functionalities implemented in the finalised ChildRescue solution. The solution includes a web platform, two mobile app versions and several APIs, both internal and external.

This second release has several additional features compared to the first one and addresses all defined user requirements regarding: user roles and organisation management, case management, alert diffusion, feedback reception, data analytics (behaviour and predictive analytics, feedback evaluation, geospatial estimations analytics), field operation and team coordination support, blockchain implementation and an intelligent search functionality. The methodology followed is fully compliant to the results of WP1 and WP2.

According to WP4 planning, the ChildRescue platform will be heavily tested by the pilot partners, before putting it to a full public release, due for launching in [M29].

Annex I: Implemented User Stories Release II

#	Epic	ACTOR	GOAL/DESIRE	BENEFIT
		As a...	I want ...	, so that...
VU.00.0	Download	Visitor	to download the light ChildRescue app	I can be informed, receive alerts and provide feedback.
VU.01.0	Registration	Visitor	to be able to register using minimal details	I can be part of the ChildRescue platform.
VU.01.2	Platform Browsing	Visitor	to be able to use the app without registering	I can still receive alerts and contribute anonymously, without having a ChildRescue account.
VU.01.3	Platform Browsing	Visitor	to be able to allow geolocation services	I can receive alerts based on my current location.
VU.02.0	Platform Browsing	Visitor	to be able to view currently active alerts near my vicinity	I can actively participate in the investigation.
VU.04.0	Platform Browsing	Visitor	to be able to visit the page with more information on a single case, when I receive notification for this case	I can view more details concerning the case.
VU.05.0	Platform Browsing	Visitor	to be able to view a list of the participating organisations and their contact details	I can communicate with organisations by other means, such as telephone or postal services.
VU.05.1	Platform Browsing	Visitor	to get informed on the process to become a volunteer for a specific organisation	I can offer my help in a more official and permanent way.
VU.06.0	Platform Browsing	Visitor	to be able to view information about the platform, terms of service and usage, etc.	I can be fully aware of what the platform is about and what requirements it involves.
VU.07.0	Platform Browsing	Visitor	to be able to view information about DOs and DON'Ts regarding missing children investigation.	I can assist the investigation in an appropriate for the child at risk manner, abiding by the law and respecting human rights.

#	Epic	ACTOR	GOAL/DESIRE	BENEFIT
		As a...	I want ...	, so that...
VU.08.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Visitor	to send geotagged (with a location I can choose from a map or my current mobile location) and timestamped feedback in the form of text and image to the organisation concerning a missing child by filling-in an appropriate form	I can assist in the investigation mission.
VU.08.1	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Visitor	to be able to submit a piece of information, even for a case I am not informed about with a localised notification (e.g. if I've seen the child via TV alert or otherwise, and I want to give information about it)	I can assist also in cases that I am not actively informed about through ChildRescue.
VU.08.2	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Visitor	to view a list with the emergency operating lines of each organisation, with a brief description, when I want to provide input regarding a child and I don't find a matching case in the list	I can assist also in cases that I am not actively informed about, in the most appropriate manner.
VU.08.3	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Visitor	to view a confirmation screen after I submit feedback	I know that the process has been successful.
SU.04.0	Profile Editing	Simple User	to be able to use my "right to be forgotten" under the GDPR, and permanently remove my account from the system	I am no longer a member of the ChildRescue platform and my personal information cannot be retrieved by any means.
SU.12.1	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Simple User	to be able to view all feedback I have submitted through the ChildRescue app	I have an overview of my actions.
SU.15.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Simple User	to get notified when there is a missing child alert in my vicinity	I can act on it and help the investigation.

#	Epic	ACTOR	GOAL/DESIRE	BENEFIT
		As a...	I want ...	, so that...
SU.16.1	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Simple User	to have the option to select and "follow" specific cases	I receive notification if case is closed.
SU.17.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Simple User	to get notified when a case I follow or had provided feedback for, is closed	I can stop any actions I have started.
FM.01.1	Investigation Profiling	Hosting Manager Facility	to match a new child profile with existing profiles using simple name search (surname, first name)	I can identify if a new coming minor has been registered before or was in another facility before.
FM.02.0	Investigation Profiling	Hosting Manager Facility	to be able to fill in profiling information about an unaccompanied migrant minor residing in the premises	I can keep track of the minors residing in the facility I am responsible for.
FM.04.1	Investigation Profiling	Hosting Manager Facility	to be able to edit the case info and the documents in the ChildRescue platform	I can easily update the record of a minor under my responsibility.
FM.04.2	Facility Management	Hosting Manager Facility	to be able to see a list of all children accommodated in a hosting facility	I can have a better overview.
CM.01.0	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to fill in the basic information about a new missing child case	I can provide basic details on that case.
CM.01.2	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to edit the case info and documents in the ChildRescue platform	I can easily find and make changes to the history of a child.
CM.01.3	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to have access to all cases of my organisation	information about the same case is not lost between different case managers and shifts.

#	Epic	ACTOR	GOAL/DESIRE	BENEFIT
		As a...	I want ...	, so that...
CM.01.6	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to find a case that is documented in the system using simple name search	I can see if it is a multiple case and a relevant record already exists in the system.
CM.02.0	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to update and extend the information of a case with more details or specify crucial information (like location last seen, latest info gathered, etc.)	I can offer an updated description of a case.
CM.02.1	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to update the open case record with received feedback, after I have approved this information	all case data is stored in a well-maintained and continuous manner.
CM.02.2	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to tag received feedback as irrelevant/relevant/credible	I can easily assess feedback.
CM.11.1	Investigation Crowd Sourcing Action	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to configure the centre, radius and duration of the alert for the crowdsourcing feedback validation process	I can focus the process.
CM.13.1	Investigation Crowd Sourcing Action	Organisation Case Manager	all notifications sent through the platform to the general public to include only information approved by the authorities	the whereabouts of the missing child cannot be inferred and malicious use of the platform is prevented.
CM.13.2	Investigation Crowd Sourcing Action	Organisation Case Manager	to configure the dissemination area and duration of the alerts that will be sent to users based on my expertise	crowdsourcing is more focused and efficient.
CM.13.3	Investigation Crowd Sourcing Action	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to change the configurations of an active alert or even deactivate it	I can have control on the alert system.
CM.13.4	Investigation Crowd Sourcing Action	Organisation Case Manager	the alert to remain on the user's mobile until it expires or is set inactive by me	the location of the alert is not easily inferred.

#	Epic	ACTOR	GOAL/DESIRE	BENEFIT
		As a...	I want ...	, so that...
CM.15.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to get feedback from all available human resources regarding a missing child case (e.g. citizens, anonymous users, volunteers)	I can gather all possible information.
CM.18.0	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Case Manager	to view all information about a case, sent by all participants, in historical order	I can have a more detailed view on the progress of the investigation.
CM.23.0	Archiving	Organisation Case Manager	the personal case data of a closed case to not be retrievable any more through ChildRescue for any user, if the child has requested it	the rights of the child on its personal data, under GDPR, are respected.
OC.01.0	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Coordinator	To have access to all cases' information and be able to edit, open or close a case	I have total control of all cases.
OC.06.1	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Coordinator	to have a basic monitoring dashboard for each case	I can understand at which state is each case and what assistance is required.
OO.01.1	Organisation Information Filling	Organisation Owner	to be able to set and edit the basic information about my organisation	I can provide an informative profile of the organisation.
CA.01.0	ChildRescue Administration	ChildRescue Administrator	to create the organisation profile and add organisation owner	the organisation can use ChildRescue.
CA.02.0	ChildRescue Administration	ChildRescue Administrator	to delete an organisation	it is no longer part of the ChildRescue platform.
SU.01.0	Registration	Simple User	to be able to specify some basic, optional personal profile information during the initial registration process	I can have a more complete and reliable personal profile which increases my integrity thus making me a trusted collaborator.
SU.02.0	Profile Editing	Simple User	to be able to edit my personal profile information	I can update my profile if any change occurs.

#	Epic			
		ACTOR	GOAL/DESIRE	BENEFIT
		As a...	I want ...	, so that...
SU.16.1	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Simple User	to have the option to select and "follow" specific cases	I receive notification if case is closed.
SU.17.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Simple User	to get notified when a case I follow or had provided feedback for, is closed	I can stop any actions I have started.
FM.01.0	Profile Editing	Hosting Facility Manager	to be able to edit my personal profile information and add more details regarding my skills, personality or general background.	I can have a more complete personal profile.
FM.04.0	Investigation Profiling	Hosting Facility Manager	to be able to upload documents to the platform concerning the children of my facility	there is a repository of profile records with the corresponding digital files (e.g. id papers, forms, departure report, etc.).
FM.05.0	Investigation Profiling	Hosting Facility Manager	to be able to edit/replace the documents I have uploaded to the platform	there is always the updated version of all pieces of information regarding a profile record.
CM.00.0	Profile Editing	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to edit my personal profile information and add more details regarding my skills, personality or general background.	I can have a more complete personal profile.
CM.01.1	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to upload a scanned document of signed consent or other relevant files (reports, testimonies, etc.)	I can have documents related to a case gathered and easily retrievable.
CM.01.2	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to edit the case info and documents in the ChildRescue platform	I can easily find and make changes to the history of a child.
CM.01.8	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Case Manager	fields of an old case for the same child to be automatically copied to a new case, and then I can check and modify them	I avoid double typing.

#	Epic	ACTOR	GOAL/DESIRE	BENEFIT
		As a...	I want ...	, so that...
CM.05.0	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to add psychological reviews, witness reports, etc.	I can enhance the profiling details of the missing child.
CM.17.1	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Case Manager	to have a basic monitoring dashboard for each case	I can understand at which state the case is.
CM.18.1	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Case Manager	cases in my dashboard to have a notification sign, if there is an unread update regarding this case	I can distinguish cases with updates which I haven't seen yet.
CM.18.1.2	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to click on a notification and directly go to the case	I can easily browse all available info on a case and better relate the notification.
CM.18.2	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Case Manager	to easily link related cases or cases of siblings	I work more efficiently but at the same time cover all possible scenarios (children are together or separated).
CM.18.3	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Case Manager	to have a list of missing people cases which are correlated (gone missing together)	I can handle a natural disaster incident efficiently and quickly.
OC.08.0	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Coordinator	to be able to view all current and past cases (that have not been removed after request of the child) and their full details	I have access to all available information.
OC.09.1	Investigation Management	Organisation Coordinator	to have a log of the activity history (alerts sent, messages sent etc.) of all administrative users (CM, FM, NM)	I have a clear overview of the taken actions and be able to allocate cases accordingly.
OC.10.0	Organisation Communication	Organisation Coordinator	to be able to allow location-based alerts to inform citizens regarding a natural disaster or emergency by having a checkbox "All information included in the message is approved by the authorities" to be checked, in order for the text message to be sent to the public, through ChildRescue	I can inform citizens, always in consultation with the authorities.

#	Epic			
		ACTOR	GOAL/DESIRE	BENEFIT
		As a...	I want ...	, so that...
OO.02.0	Organisation Management	Organisation Owner	to be able to view a list of members of my organisation and at what position and general location	I can have an overview of our human resources assignments.
OO.05.0	Organisation Management	Organisation Owner	to remove users from my organisation	I can re-organise our human resources.
VU.01.1	Registration	Visitor	to have the option to register by using social media accounts	I can be part of the ChildRescue platform.
VU.02.1	Platform Browsing	Visitor	to have only one active alert per case	I have a clear overview of cases and my device is not spammed with notifications.
VU.03.0	Platform Browsing	Visitor	to sort the list of alerts on my app based on the disappearance date of the child	I can see the most recent ones.
SU.11.1	Platform Browsing	Simple User	to see statistics (e.g. cases solved per country) in front page if there are no active cases in vicinity, or as menu item if there are	I have a general picture of the work done by the organisations.
FM.05.1	Investigation Profiling	Hosting Facility Manager	to be able to mark the absence of a minor living in my hosting facility	I can have an easier overview of the facility and the hosted minors.
FM.05.3	Facility Management	Hosting Facility Manager	the system to be updated regarding vacancies in my hosting facility	everyone responsible is easily informed and can decide on the distribution of the applications for hosting.
FM.07.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Hosting Facility Manager	to be able to have all historical data of the child under the same case (e.g. previous facilities stayed at)	I can have complete and consistent information about the child, and can extract possible POIs.

#	Epic	ACTOR	GOAL/DESIRE	BENEFIT
		As a...	I want ...	, so that...
FM.10.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Hosting Facility Manager	to have access to the collaboration space so that I get guidance and information about the case	I can be constantly informed about the case's status and act in a more efficient way.
CM.01.31	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to have a prioritised view of the cases based on urgency (amber alert, simple alert, feedback given)	I have a better overview of the cases and most important/urgent ones have a better ranking.
CM.01.4	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to match a new child profile with existing profiles using multiple criteria, fuzzy matching and intelligent methods	I can check if it's a multiple case or if there is an active tracing request.
CM.01.5	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to find a case that is documented in the system using multiple profiling criteria and fuzzy matching	I can see if it is a multiple case, or there are other cases with strong resemblance.
CM.01.7	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	profiling fields that are common with other existing systems of the organisation (ex. CRM), to automatically take input from these systems through API end-points (if available)	I avoid double typing.
CM.04.0	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to add social media accounts of the child and relevant information	I can enhance the profiling process by using knowledge extraction on social profile preferences, activities, public posts, etc., in alignment with GDPR.
CM.05.1	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to perform profiling analytics	I can have insights and predictions on behavioural patterns of the case.
CM.07.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to engage in discussions with user groups (e.g. volunteers, rescue teams) regarding the same case and a specific location	I can carry forward relevant information in a secure and private virtual space and exchange real-time messages.

#	Epic	ACTOR	GOAL/DESIRE	BENEFIT
		As a...	I want ...	, so that...
CM.07.1	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to set up a collaboration space dedicated to the missing child case and uniquely identified by the given search area (note: we may have multiple search areas for the same case)	I can invite rescue and volunteer teams close to the area, monitor and manage them.
CM.08.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to upload/download files of information in the collaboration space	I can exchange multimedia files, like photos or videos, with the case members.
CM.12.0	Investigation Crowd Sourcing Action	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to configure the settings of the feedback evaluation validation process	I can evaluate a piece of information based on criteria of my choice.
CM.16.0	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to view and explore open data	to get more and location-related information about transportation, weather etc.
CM.17.0	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Case Manager	to monitor the overall progress of the investigation	I can understand at which state it is.
CM.18.4	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Case Manager	to ensure that all feedback from mobile users will remain logged and unchanged	the platform operates based on integrity and trust.
CM.20.0	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to upload my evaluation report for the Coordinator to view	the important information propagates to the top.
CM.20.1	Archiving	Organisation Case Manager	to archive a closed case	the case is removed from the active cases list, is appropriately tagged and can be used as a new input in analytics.
CM.20.2	Archiving	Organisation Case Manager	to mark as true or false all received feedback on a finished case	I can use this information for analytics.

# Epic				
		ACTOR	GOAL/DESIRE	BENEFIT
		As a...	I want ...	, so that...
CM.20.3	Archiving	Organisation Case Manager	to semantically tag a closed case	it can be easier matched to similar past or future cases.
CM.22.0	Archiving	Organisation Case Manager	the case data of a closed case to be deleted from the mobile users' devices within a fixed period of time	the privacy of the child and family is protected after closure.
RT.00.0	Registration	S&R/Volunteer Team Member	to be able to sign in to the enhanced app for rescue teams following a two-step verification process	I can have access to the S&R/ operational/coordination functionalities of ChildRescue in a safe manner.
RT.01.0	Profile Editing	S&R/Volunteer Team Member	to be able to edit my personal profile information and add more details regarding my skills, personality or general background.	I can have a more complete personal profile.
RT.02.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	S&R/Volunteer Team Member	to get notified when there is a missing child case and my contribution is required	I can act on it and help the investigation in the field.
RT.02.1	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	S&R/Volunteer Team Member	to be able to decline an invitation to join investigation team and continue as a simple user for this specific case if at all	if I am not able to actively participate as a team member, still be able to help and receive location-based notifications as any simple registered user.
RT.03.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	S&R/Volunteer Team Member	to have access to a collaboration space with other team-members and case coordinators	I can communicate with my team in a secure and private virtual space.
RT.03.1	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	S&R/Volunteer Team Member	to be able to turn my geolocation off temporarily, but continue receiving the messages and notifications of the discussion team	I can pause and rest from an active investigation I am taking part in, but still be updated with latest news.

#	Epic	ACTOR	GOAL/DESIRE	BENEFIT
		As a...	I want ...	, so that...
RT.03.2	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	S&R/Volunteer Team Member	to be able to quit from an investigation case and the related collaboration space	I can disengage from the search operations of this case and the respective team's affairs.
RT.05.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	S&R/Volunteer Team Member	to get guidance and announcements about the case from my superiors	I can be constantly informed about the case's status and act in a more efficient way.
RT.05.1	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	S&R/Volunteer Team Member	to have a list of actions to perform and be able to mark them when done	I have a clear overview of what I have to do.
TL.01.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	S&R/Volunteer Team Leader	to be able to watch my current location, as well as other teams/team members' locations, on an interactive map	I can have a clear overview of the team's current situation and the area each member covers.
TL.02.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	S&R/Volunteer Team Leader	to get guidance and announcements about the case from coordinators	I can be constantly informed about the case's status and act in a more efficient way.
TL.03.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	S&R/Volunteer Team Leader	to have access to a collaboration space with teams and case coordinators with the ability to upload/download files	I can offer the necessary information (e.g. a profile record) to the investigation group or my superiors.
NM.01.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	To get notified as soon as there is a new case that requires my skills	I can act rapidly to assemble the appropriate teams.

#	Epic	ACTOR	GOAL/DESIRE	BENEFIT
		As a...	I want ...	, so that...
NM.02.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	to be able to invite available Volunteer/S&R members, to join the collaboration space	we can setup a collaboration space about the case and the investigation.
NM.02.1	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	to be able to notify with free-text message all volunteers of local S&R Teams or/and Volunteer Teams of the new case and receive their availability	I can setup teams for the investigations and give volunteers some basic contact details.
NM.02.2	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	to receive a confirmation of delivery for every invitation I have sent to volunteers	I know if my notification has reached the members.
NM.02.3	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	to be able to manually assign the team leader of every volunteer/S&R team from the available members	it is easier to coordinate separate teams.
NM.02.5	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	to be able to notify new members and teams to join the collaboration space according to the investigation progress, especially if a new geographical location is suggested	adequate rescuers and volunteers are participating in each stage and place of the investigation.
NM.03.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	to be able to engage in discussions with selected team leaders and case managers	I can guide my teams in a secure and private virtual space.
NM.03.1	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	to be able to post announcements for all team members participating in the case to view, similar to a news feed	I can give one-way instructions to the teams, which will be easily viewable.

#	Epic			
		ACTOR	GOAL/DESIRE	BENEFIT
		As a...	I want ...	, so that...
NM.03.2	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	to mark important announcements in the timeline with different colour (highlight)	the volunteers can easily see what I think is important.
NM.03.3	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	assign actions to be performed to participating team members	they can have a clear view of what they have to do.
NM.03.4	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	to create discussions with selected members from the volunteer/S&R teams for communications	I can instantly exchange information with team leaders.
NM.05.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	to be able to contact and get guidance by the Organisation Coordinator	I can be constantly informed about all cases' status and distribute human resources accordingly and more efficiently.
NM.06.0	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Network Manager	to be able to view where all field resources (humans, vehicles, dogs) are located	I can be constantly informed about the status and whereabouts of all field resources.
NM.07.0	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Network Manager	to monitor the current progress of the investigation location-wise	I can direct teams to search in specific areas.
NM.08.0	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Network Manager	to view predictions regarding the possible POIs related to the missing child	I can direct teams to search in specific areas.
NM.09.0	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Network Manager	to be able to send my evaluation and current status to the Coordinator	the important information propagates to the top.

#	Epic	ACTOR	GOAL/DESIRE	BENEFIT
		As a...	I want ...	, so that...
OC.02.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Coordinator	to be able to communicate with all Case and Network Managers through the collaboration space.	I can coordinate all available resources.
OC.02.1	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Coordinator	to be able to access case-related files and documents	I can view more explicit case information and reporting.
OC.02.2	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Coordinator	to be able to send the case files and documents to organisations in another country	I can rapidly inform and activate legitimate organisations in case of a cross-border country.
OC.03.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Coordinator	to be able to exchange messages with users in the collaboration space (e.g. volunteers, rescue teams)	I can carry forward relevant information in a secure and private virtual space.
OC.05.0	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Coordinator	to be able to contact the mobile users of the platform personally	I can send and get information directly from users.
OC.06.0	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Coordinator	to monitor the overall progress of all the active investigations per location	I can understand at which state is each case and what assistance is required.
OC.09.0	Investigation Management	Organisation Coordinator	to be able to assign Case and Network Managers for each case	each case is covered in the most efficient way.
OC.11.0	Archiving	Organisation Coordinator	to aggregate data from past cases	useful outcomes are provided to be exploited in the future, in a manner always respecting privacy issues.

#	Epic	ACTOR	GOAL/DESIRE	BENEFIT
		As a...	I want ...	, so that...
OC.12.0	Archiving	Organisation Coordinator	statistics to be generated from every case and to be correlated	I gain insights in the performance of the organisation.
OO.01.0	Organisation Information Filling	Organisation Owner	to receive invitation to activate my organisation's profile in ChildRescue	I take control of the new profile and start managing it.
OO.03.0	Organisation Management	Organisation Owner	to be able to send invitation e-mails to my personnel and associated with their new accounts in the platform	they join the platform and I can gather all my human resources in this collaboration platform.
OO.04.0	Organisation Management	Organisation Owner	to create profiles in the ChildRescue platform for administrative users of my organisation (OC, CM, FM, NM)	I can add admins of my organisation to the platform.
OO.04.1	Organisation Management	Organisation Owner	To setup organisation facilities and assign members in each one	I can have all of my members assigned to one location (facility) for better management.
OO.07.0	Organisation Monitoring	Organisation Owner	to have an overview of all active cases and the human resources (e.g. organisation members, volunteers, etc.) assigned on each one	I can have a clear picture of the current effort and possible deficiencies.
OO.08.0	Organisation Monitoring	Organisation Owner	to have an overview of the duration of all historical cases and the human resources assigned on each one	I can have a clear picture of the past performance of my staff.
OO.10.0	Organisation Communication	Organisation Owner	to be able to communicate with other organisations using their e-mail	we can cooperate together in a mission or cause.
OO.11.0	Organisation Policy	Organisation Owner	all case data to be anonymised if there is a request related to the "right to be forgotten" according to GDPR.	the privacy of the family and the child are protected and my organisation is aligned to the GDPR requirements.
OO.12.0	Organisation Policy	Organisation Owner	all case data to be encrypted	I ensure my organisation's policies regarding personal and private data.

Annex II: Integration test tables

Table II-1: User Registration Integration Test

Component	MobileApp.DataHandler
REST endpoint	http://157.230.102.159:8082/mobile/api/v1/users/register/
Method	POST
Caller	Call<User> createUser(@Field("first_name") String name, @Field("last_name") String lastName, @Field("email") String email, @Field("password") String password)
Unit test	<pre> package eu.ubitech.childrescue; import org.junit.Test; import java.io.IOException; import eu.ubitech.childrescue.entity.User; import eu.ubitech.childrescue.rest.ChildRescueAPIClient; import eu.ubitech.childrescue.rest.IChildRescueAPI; import retrofit2.Call; import retrofit2.Response; import static org.junit.Assert.assertTrue; public class RegisterUserTest { @Test public void testRegisterUser() { IChildRescueAPI apiService = ChildRescueAPIClient.getClient("").create(IChildRescueAPI.class); String firstName = "test"; String lastName = "user"; String email = "usertest@test.com"; String password = "user"; Call<User> call = apiService.createUser(firstName, lastName, email, password); try { Response<User> response = call.execute(); User userResponse = response.body(); assertTrue(response.isSuccessful() && userResponse != null); System.out.println(response.headers()); } catch (IOException e) { e.printStackTrace(); } } } </pre>

	<pre> } } } </pre>
Request headers	<pre> Request originalRequest = chain.request(); Request.Builder builder = originalRequest.newBuilder() .header("Accept", "application/json") .header("Content-type", "application/json") .header("Authorization", "Bearer " + authorizationToken) .method(originalRequest.method(), originalRequest.body()); </pre>
Valid JSON Input sample	<pre> { "first_name": "test", "last_name": "user", "email": "usertest@test.com", "password": "user" } </pre>
Response headers	<pre> Server: nginx/1.10.3 (Ubuntu) Date: Mon, 24 Jun 2019 14:38:26 GMT Content-Type: application/json Content-Length: 117 Connection: keep-alive Allow: POST, OPTIONS Vary: Accept, Cookie X-Frame-Options: SAMEORIGIN </pre>
Response body	<pre> { "id": 25, "email": "usertest@test.com", "first_name": "test", "last_name": "user", "profile_image": null, "is_end_user": false } </pre>

Table II-2: Receive Information for Specific Case Integration Test

Component	MobileApp.DataHandler
REST endpoint	http://157.230.102.159:8082/api/v1/cases/mobile_api/{id}/feed/
Method	GET
Caller	Call<List<Post>> fetchFeeds(@Path("id") Integer caseId);
Unit test	<pre> package eu.ubitech.childrescue.volunteer; import org.junit.Test; import static org.junit.Assert.*; import java.io.IOException; import java.util.List; import eu.ubitech.childrescue.volunteer.entity.Post; import eu.ubitech.childrescue.volunteer.rest.ChildRescueAPIClient; import eu.ubitech.childrescue.volunteer.rest.IChildRescueAPI; import retrofit2.Call; import retrofit2.Response; public class GetFeedsForCaseTest { @Test public void testFeeds() { Integer caseId = 10; String authToken = "{authorizationToken}"; IChildRescueAPI apiService = ChildRescueAPIClient.getClient(authToken).create(IChildRescueAPI.class); Call<List<Post>> call = apiService.fetchFeeds(caseId); try { Response<List<Post>> response = call.execute(); List<Post> listResponse = response.body(); assertTrue(response.isSuccessful() && !listResponse.isEmpty()); System.out.println(response.headers()); </pre>

	<pre> } catch (IOException e) { e.printStackTrace(); } } } </pre>
Request headers	<pre> Request originalRequest = chain.request(); Request.Builder builder = originalRequest.newBuilder() .header("Accept", "application/json") .header("Content-type", "application/json") .header("Authorization", "Bearer " + authorizationToken) .method(originalRequest.method(), originalRequest.body()); </pre>
Valid JSON Input sample	<pre> { "id": "10" } </pre>
Response headers	<pre> Server: nginx/1.14.0 (Ubuntu) Date: Thu, 26 Mar 2020 22:13:13 GMT Content-Type: application/json Content-Length: 19757 Connection: keep-alive Vary: Accept, Origin, Cookie Allow: GET, POST, HEAD, OPTIONS X-Frame-Options: SAMEORIGIN </pre>
Response body	<pre> [{ "id": 18, "name": "Smile Org", "description": "test", "tag": "task", "is_visible_to_volunteers": true, "image": null, "address": null, "latitude": null, "longitude": null, "radius": 5.0, "created_at": "2019-12-16T12:54:21.873698Z", "updated_at": "2019-12-16T12:54:21.873731Z", "user": 2, "case": 10 }] </pre>

Table II-3: Receive Alert Integration Test

Component	MobileApp.DataHandler
REST endpoint	http://157.230.102.159:8082/api/v1/alerts/mobile_api/
Method	GET
Caller	Call<List<Alert>> fetchAreaAlerts(@Query("latitude") String latitude, @Query("longitude") String longitude, @Query("uuid") String uuid, @Query("device") String device)
Unit test	<pre> package eu.ubitech.childrescue.volunteer; import org.junit.Test; import static org.junit.Assert.*; import java.io.IOException; import java.util.List; import eu.ubitech.childrescue.volunteer.entity.Alert; import eu.ubitech.childrescue.volunteer.rest.ChildRescueAPIClient; import eu.ubitech.childrescue.volunteer.rest.IChildRescueAPI; import retrofit2.Call; import retrofit2.Response; public class GetAreaAlertsTest { @Test public void testReceiveAlerts() { IChildRescueAPI apiService = ChildRescueAPIClient.getClient("").create(IChildRescueAPI.class); String latitude = "38.040411"; String longitude = "23.689903"; String uuid = "{uuid}"; String device = "android"; Call<List<Alert>> call = apiService.fetchAreaAlerts(latitude, longitude, uuid, device); try { Response<List<Alert>> response = call.execute(); List<Alert> listResponse = response.body(); </pre>

	<pre> assertTrue(response.isSuccessful() && !listResponse.isEmpty()); System.out.println(response.headers()); } catch (IOException e) { e.printStackTrace(); } } } </pre>
Request headers	<pre> Request originalRequest = chain.request(); Request.Builder builder = originalRequest.newBuilder() .header("Accept", "application/json") .header("Content-type", "application/json") .header("Authorization", "Bearer " + authorizationToken) .method(originalRequest.method(), originalRequest.body()); </pre>
Valid JSON Input sample	<pre> { "latitude": "38.024813", "longitude": "23.848919", "uuid": "{uuid}", "device": "android" } </pre>
Response headers	<pre> Server: nginx/1.14.0 (Ubuntu) Date: Thu, 26 Mar 2020 21:05:31 GMT Content-Type: application/json Content-Length: 543 Connection: keep-alive Vary: Accept, Origin, Cookie Allow: GET, HEAD, OPTIONS X-Frame-Options: SAMEORIGIN </pre>
Response body	<pre> [{ "id": 32, "case": 20, "geolocation_point": "SRID=4326;POINT (38.0331754 23.6961759)", "latitude": 38.0331754, "longitude": 23.6961759, "address": "petroupolews petroupoli", "radius": 2.0, "start": "2020-03-26T21:00:56.219000Z", "end": "2020-03-26T23:00:56.219000Z", }] </pre>

	<pre> "is_active": true, "description": "test", "created_at": "2020-03-26T21:00:56.545215Z", "updated_at": "2020-03-26T21:00:56.545233Z", "fullname": "New test", "disappearance_date": "", "date_of_birth": null, "eye_color": null, "hair_color": null, "height": null, "weight": null, "image": "http://157.230.102.159:8082/media/" } </pre>
Execution results	<p>The screenshot shows a test runner interface with the following details:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Test Name: GetAreaAlertsTest (eu.ubitech.childrescue 1 s 196ms) Method: testReceiveAlerts (1 s 196ms) Status: Tests passed: 1 of 1 test - 1 s 196ms Server: nginx/1.14.0 (Ubuntu) Date: Thu, 26 Mar 2020 21:05:31 GMT Content-Type: application/json Content-Length: 543 Connection: keep-alive Vary: Accept, Origin, Cookie Allow: GET, HEAD, OPTIONS X-Frame-Options: SAMEORIGIN

Table II-4: Send Feedback Integration Test

Component	MobileApp.DataHandler
REST endpoint	http://157.230.102.159:8082/api/v1/feedbacks/mobile_api/
Method	POST
Caller	<pre> Call<ProvidedFeedback> provideInfo(@Part("user") RequestBody userId, @Part("case") RequestBody caseId, @Part("current_longitude") RequestBody userLong, @Part("current_latitude") RequestBody userLat, @Part("longitude") RequestBody caseLong, @Part("latitude") RequestBody caseLat, @Part("comment") RequestBody description, @Part("date") RequestBody date, @Part("address") RequestBody address, @Part MultipartBody.Part image); </pre>

Unit test	<pre>package eu.ubitech.childrescue.volunteer; import org.junit.Test; import java.io.IOException; import eu.ubitech.childrescue.volunteer.entity.ProvidedFeedback; import eu.ubitech.childrescue.volunteer.rest.ChildRescueAPIClient; import eu.ubitech.childrescue.volunteer.rest.IChildRescueAPI; import okhttp3.MediaType; import okhttp3.MultipartBody; import okhttp3.RequestBody; import retrofit2.Call; import retrofit2.Response; import static org.junit.Assert.assertTrue; public class ProvideFeedbackTest { @Test public void testProvideFeedback() { IChildRescueAPI apiService = ChildRescueAPIClient.getClient("").create(IChildRescueAPI.class); Integer userId = 1; Integer caseId = 1; String current_latitude = "38.024813"; String current_longitude = "23.848919"; String case_latitude = "38.024813"; String case_longitude = "23.848919"; String description = "test"; String date = "2020-06-12T20:00:00Z"; RequestBody user = RequestBody.create(MediaType.parse("text/plain"), String.valueOf(userId)); RequestBody caseID = RequestBody.create(MediaType.parse("text/plain"), String.valueOf(caseId)); RequestBody userLong = RequestBody.create(MediaType.parse("text/plain"), current_longitude); RequestBody userLat = RequestBody.create(MediaType.parse("text/plain"), current_latitude); RequestBody caseLongitude = RequestBody.create(MediaType.parse("text/plain"), case_longitude); RequestBody caseLatitude = RequestBody.create(MediaType.parse("text/plain"), case_latitude); RequestBody desc = RequestBody.create(MediaType.parse("text/plain"), description); RequestBody dateTime = RequestBody.create(MediaType.parse("text/plain"), date); RequestBody addressName = RequestBody.create(MediaType.parse("text/plain"), ""); MultipartBody.Part image = null;</pre>
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	<pre> Call<ProvidedFeedback> call = apiService.provideInfo(user, caseID, userLong, userLat, caseLongitude, caseLatitude, desc, dateTime, addressName, null); try { Response<ProvidedFeedback> response = call.execute(); ProvidedFeedback feedbackResponse = response.body(); assertTrue(response.isSuccessful() && feedbackResponse != null); System.out.println(response.headers()); } catch (IOException e) { e.printStackTrace(); } } } </pre>
Request headers	<pre> Request originalRequest = chain.request(); Request.Builder builder = originalRequest.newBuilder() .header("Accept", "application/json") .header("Content-type", "application/json") .header("Authorization", "Bearer " + authorizationToken) .method(originalRequest.method(), originalRequest.body()); </pre>
Valid JSON Input sample	<pre> { "userId":1, "caseId":1, "current_longitude":"23.848919", "current_latitude":"38.024813", "case_longitude":"23.848919", "case_latitude":"38.024813", "description":"test", "date":"2019-06-12T20:00:00", "address":""," "image": } </pre>
Response headers	<pre> Server: nginx/1.14.0 (Ubuntu) Date: Thu, 26 Mar 2020 21:38:56 GMT Content-Type: application/json Content-Length: 610 Connection: keep-alive Vary: Accept, Origin, Cookie Allow: GET, POST, HEAD, OPTIONS </pre>

	X-Frame-Options: SAMEORIGIN
Response body	<pre>{ "id": 123, "source": "Anonymous", "latitude": 38.024813, "longitude": 23.848919, "current_latitude": 38.024813, "current_longitude": 23.848919, "comment": "test", "feedback_image": null, "address": null, "date": "2019-06-12T20:00:00Z", "created_at": "2020-03-26T22:12:36.343305Z", "updated_at": "2020-03-26T22:12:52.343323Z", "checked_on": null, "feedback_status": "pending", "is_valid": null, "location_selected_reasons": null, "child_status": null, "transportation": null, "case": 1, "alert": null, "user": 1, "checked_by": null }</pre>
Execution results	

Table II-5: Send Information for Specific Case Integration Test

Component	MobileApp.DataHandler
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REST endpoint	http://157.230.102.159:8082/api/v1/cases/mobile_api/{id}/feed/
Method	POST
Caller	Call<Post> provideFeed(@Path("id") Integer caseId, @Part("longitude") RequestBody userLong, @Part("latitude") RequestBody userLat, @Part("tag") RequestBody tag, @Part("description") RequestBody description, @Part MultipartBody.Part image);
Unit test	<pre> package eu.ubitech.childrescue.volunteer; import org.junit.Test; import java.io.IOException; import eu.ubitech.childrescue.volunteer.entity.Post; import eu.ubitech.childrescue.volunteer.rest.ChildRescueAPIClient; import eu.ubitech.childrescue.volunteer.rest.IChildRescueAPI; import okhttp3.MediaType; import okhttp3.RequestBody; import retrofit2.Call; import retrofit2.Response; import static org.junit.Assert.assertTrue; public class ProvideFeedTest { @Test public void testProvideFeed() { String authToken = "sM8hJDtK25DJygJP6YYVIEdTf7Dy3P"; IChildRescueAPI apiService = ChildRescueAPIClient.getClient(authToken).create(IChildRescueAPI.class); Integer caseId = 10; String current_latitude = "38.024813"; String current_longitude = "23.848919"; String tag = "announcement"; String description = "test announcement"; RequestBody userLong = RequestBody.create(MediaType.parse("text/plain"), current_longitude); RequestBody userLat = RequestBody.create(MediaType.parse("text/plain"), current_latitude); RequestBody desc = RequestBody.create(MediaType.parse("text/plain"), description); RequestBody tagName = RequestBody.create(MediaType.parse("text/plain"), tag); Call<Post> call = apiService.provideFeed(caseId, userLong, userLat, tagName, desc, null); try { Response<Post> response = call.execute(); Post feedbackResponse = response.body(); </pre>

	<pre> assertTrue(response.isSuccessful() && feedbackResponse != null); System.out.println(response.headers()); } catch (IOException e) { e.printStackTrace(); } } } </pre>
Request headers	<pre> Request originalRequest = chain.request(); Request.Builder builder = originalRequest.newBuilder() .header("Accept", "application/json") .header("Content-type", "application/json") .header("Authorization", "Bearer " + authorizationToken) .method(originalRequest.method(), originalRequest.body()); </pre>
Valid JSON Input sample	<pre> { "caseId":1, "current_longitude":"23.848919", "current_latitude":"38.024813", "tag":"test announcement", "description":"test announcement", "image": } </pre>
Response headers	<pre> Server: nginx/1.14.0 (Ubuntu) Date: Thu, 26 Mar 2020 22:59:47 GMT Content-Type: application/json Content-Length: 314 Connection: keep-alive Vary: Accept, Origin, Cookie Allow: GET, POST, HEAD, OPTIONS X-Frame-Options: SAMEORIGIN </pre>
Response body	<pre> { "id": 115, "name": "George Vafeiadis", "description": "test announcement", "tag": " announcement ", "is_visible_to_volunteers": false, "image": null, "address": null, "latitude": 38.024813, </pre>

	<pre> "longitude": 23.848919, "radius": 5.0, "created_at": "2020-03-26T22:59:47.243305Z", "updated_at": "2020-03-26T23:03:43.243323Z", "user": 27, "case": 10 </pre>
<p>Execution results</p>	

Annex III: Performance test tables

Login

This request represents the login process of an authenticated user.

HTTP Request	Login
Request headers	Connection: close Host: 157.230.102.159:8082 Content-Type: application/x-www-form-urlencoded Accept-Encoding: gzip User-Agent: okhttp/3.10.0 Content-Length: 96
Request Body	POST data: email=giovaf%40test.com&password={password}&uuid={generated uuid}&device=android
Response headers	HTTP/1.1 200 OK Server: nginx/1.14.0 (Ubuntu) Date: Thu, 26 Mar 2020 09:27:13 GMT Content-Type: application/json Content-Length: 163 Connection: close Vary: Accept, Origin, Cookie Allow: POST, OPTIONS X-Frame-Options: SAMEORIGIN
Response body	<pre>{ "access_token": "{authorization token}", "expires_in": 31536000, "token_type": "Bearer", "scope": "read write", "refresh_token": "{refresh token}" }</pre>

<p>Sampler result</p> <p>result</p>	<div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px;"> <div style="display: flex; border-bottom: 1px solid #ccc;"> Sampler result Request Response data </div> <div style="padding: 5px;"> <pre> Thread Name: Sample Start:2020-03-26 11:27:13 EET Load time:593 Connect Time:75 Latency:593 Size in bytes:403 Sent bytes:311 Headers size in bytes:240 Body size in bytes:163 Sample Count:1 Error Count:0 Data type ("text "bin ""):text Response code:200 Response message:OK HTTPSampleResult fields: ContentType: application/json DataEncoding: null </pre> </div> <div style="display: flex; margin-top: 5px;"> Raw Parsed </div> </div>
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User account

This request represents the information which is related to a specific user’s account.

HTTP Request	GET User’s account info
Request headers	Connection: close Authorization: Bearer {authorization token} Host: 157.230.102.159:8082 Content-type: application/json Accept-Encoding: gzip Accept: application/json User-Agent: okhttp/3.10.0
Request Body	GET http://157.230.102.159:8082/api/v1/users/mobile_api/me/
Response headers	HTTP/1.1 200 OK Server: nginx/1.14.0 (Ubuntu) Date: Thu, 26 Mar 2020 09:27:13 GMT Content-Type: application/json Content-Length: 121 Connection: close Vary: Accept, Origin, Cookie Allow: GET, PUT, PATCH, DELETE, HEAD, OPTIONS X-Frame-Options: SAMEORIGIN

Response body	<pre>{ "id": 27, "email": "giovaf@test.com", "first_name": "George", "last_name": "Vafeiadis", "profile_image": null, "is_end_user": true }</pre>
Sampler result	

Alerts

It represents the generated alerts which are close to the user's location.

HTTP Request	GET Alerts
Request headers	<p>Connection: close</p> <p>Authorization: Bearer {authorization token}</p> <p>Host: 157.230.102.159:8082</p> <p>Content-type: application/json</p> <p>Accept-Encoding: gzip</p> <p>Accept: application/json</p> <p>User-Agent: okhttp/3.10.0</p>
Request Body	<p>http://157.230.102.159:8082/api/v1/alerts/mobile_api/?latitude=38.0409981&longitude=23.6868846&uuid={uuid}&device=android</p>
Response headers	<p>HTTP/1.1 200 OK</p> <p>Server: nginx/1.14.0 (Ubuntu)</p> <p>Date: Thu, 26 Mar 2020 09:27:13 GMT</p>

	<p>Content-Type: application/json Content-Length: 2 Connection: close Vary: Accept, Origin, Cookie Allow: GET, HEAD, OPTIONS X-Frame-Options: SAMEORIGIN</p>
Response body	[]
Sampler result	<p>The screenshot shows a network sampler result for an HTTP response. The 'Request' tab is selected. The details include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Thread Name: Sample Start: 2020-03-26 11:27:13 EET Load time: 357 Connect Time: 74 Latency: 357 Size in bytes: 245 Sent bytes: 350 Headers size in bytes: 243 Body size in bytes: 2 Sample Count: 1 Error Count: 0 Data type ("text" "bin" ""): text Response code: 200 Response message: OK <p>Below these details, the 'HTTPSampleResult' fields are listed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ContentType: application/json DataEncoding: null <p>At the bottom, there are buttons for 'Raw' and 'Parsed'.</p>

Organizations

This request represents the retrieval of the organizations which are involved in ChildRescue.

HTTP Request	GET Organizations
Request headers	<p>Connection: close Authorization: Bearer {authorization token} Host: 157.230.102.159:8082 Content-type: application/json Accept-Encoding: gzip Accept: application/json User-Agent: okhttp/3.10.0</p>
Request Body	GET http://157.230.102.159:8082/api/v1/organizations/mobile_api/
Response headers	<p>HTTP/1.1 200 OK Server: nginx/1.14.0 (Ubuntu)</p>

	<p>Date: Thu, 26 Mar 2020 09:27:13 GMT Content-Type: application/json Content-Length: 1208 Connection: close Vary: Accept, Origin, Cookie Allow: GET, HEAD, OPTIONS X-Frame-Options: SAMEORIGIN</p>
Response body	<pre>[{ "id": 2, "name": "Hellenic Red Cross TEST", "email": "", "address": "", "phone": "", "facebook": "", "instagram": "", "twitter": "", "how_to_become_volunteer": "", "missing_child_actions": "", "description": "", "logo": null, "created_at": "2019-12-11T14:07:31.318467Z", "updated_at": "2019-12-11T14:07:31.318504Z" }]</pre>
Sampler result	<p>Sampler result Request Response data</p> <p>Thread Name: Sample Start:2020-03-26 11:27:14 EET Load time:213 Connect Time:74 Latency:212 Size in bytes:1454 Sent bytes:259 Headers size in bytes:246 Body size in bytes:1208 Sample Count:1 Error Count:0 Data type ("text" "bin" ""):text Response code:200 Response message:OK</p> <p>HTTPSampleResult fields: ContentType: application/json DataEncoding: null</p> <p>Raw Parsed</p>

Volunteer Cases

This request represents the cases in which the volunteer user is involved.

HTTP Request	GET Cases of Volunteer
Request headers	Connection: close Authorization: Bearer {authorization token} Host: 157.230.102.159:8082 Content-type: application/json Accept-Encoding: gzip Accept: application/json User-Agent: okhttp/3.10.0
Request Body	GET http://157.230.102.159:8082/api/v1/cases/mobile_api/volunteer-cases/?has_accept_invitation=True
Response headers	HTTP/1.1 200 OK Server: nginx/1.14.0 (Ubuntu) Date: Thu, 26 Mar 2020 09:27:13 GMT Content-Type: application/json Content-Length: 1930 Connection: close Vary: Accept, Origin, Cookie Allow: GET, HEAD, OPTIONS X-Frame-Options: SAMEORIGIN
Response body	[{ "id": 14, "image": "http://157.230.102.159:8082/media/cases/9/U9H9GLACTU2WYQFO80WBIRSMOR IRAFBS.jpg", "child_name": "test name", "is_amber_alert": false, "first_name": "George", "last_name": "Vafeiadis", "email": "giovaf@test.com", "has_accept_invitation": true, "is_team_leader": true, "team_name": "a3", "created_at": "2019-12-13T14:04:18.923929Z", "updated_at": "2019-12-13T14:05:21.343616Z", "case": 9, "user": 27 }]

Sampler result	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px;"> <div style="display: flex; border-bottom: 1px solid black;"> Sampler result Request Response data </div> <pre> Thread Name: Sample Start:2020-03-26 11:27:14 EET Load time:294 Connect Time:74 Latency:294 Size in bytes:2176 Sent bytes:294 Headers size in bytes:246 Body size in bytes:1930 Sample Count:1 Error Count:0 Data type ("text" "bin" ""):text Response code:200 Response message:OK HTTPSampleResult fields: ContentType: application/json DataEncoding: null </pre> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: flex-end; margin-top: 10px;"> Raw Parsed </div> </div>
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Feeds

This request represents the information which has been sent to the user by the Network Manager for a specific case.

HTTP Request	Get feedback from Network/Organization Manager
Request headers	Connection: close Authorization: Bearer {authorization token} Host: 157.230.102.159:8082 Content-type: application/json Accept-Encoding: gzip Accept: application/json User-Agent: okhttp/3.10.0
Request Body	GET http://157.230.102.159:8082/api/v1/cases/mobile_api/10/feed/
Response headers	HTTP/1.1 200 OK Server: nginx/1.14.0 (Ubuntu) Date: Thu, 26 Mar 2020 09:27:46 GMT Content-Type: application/json Content-Length: 19757 Connection: close Vary: Accept, Origin, Cookie Allow: GET, POST, HEAD, OPTIONS X-Frame-Options: SAMEORIGIN

Response body	<pre>[{ "id": 18, "name": "Smile Org", "description": "test", "tag": "task", "is_visible_to_volunteers": true, "image": null, "address": null, "latitude": null, "longitude": null, "radius": 5.0, "created_at": "2019-12-16T12:54:21.873698Z", "updated_at": "2019-12-16T12:54:21.873731Z", "user": 2, "case": 10 }, { "id": 19, "name": "Smile Org", "description": null, "tag": "general", "is_visible_to_volunteers": true, "image": null, "address": "aitolias 20, chalandri", "latitude": 38.0089867, "longitude": 23.7959597, "radius": 5.0, "created_at": "2019-12-16T12:57:29.705156Z", "updated_at": "2019-12-16T12:57:29.705186Z", "user": 2, "case": 10 }, { "id": 20, "name": "Smile Org", "description": "test", "tag": "fact", "is_visible_to_volunteers": true, "image": null, "address": null, "latitude": null, "longitude": null, "radius": 5.0, "created_at": "2019-12-16T12:59:30.793209Z", "updated_at": "2019-12-16T12:59:30.793239Z", "user": 2,</pre>
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	<pre>"case": 10 }]</pre>
Sampler result	<pre>Sampler result Request Response data Thread Name: Sample Start:2020-03-26 11:27:46 EET Load time:343 Connect Time:72 Latency:268 Size in bytes:20010 Sent bytes:259 Headers size in bytes:253 Body size in bytes:19757 Sample Count:1 Error Count:0 Data type ("text" "bin" ""):text Response code:200 Response message:OK HTTPSsampleResult fields: ContentType: application/json DataEncoding: null Raw Parsed</pre>

My feed

It represents the information which has been sent to Network Manager by a Volunteer for a specific case.

HTTP Request	Get feedback sent by Volunteer
Request headers	<pre>Connection: close Authorization: Bearer {authorization token} Host: 157.230.102.159:8082 Content-type: application/json Accept-Encoding: gzip Accept: application/json User-Agent: okhttp/3.10.0</pre>
Request Body	GET http://157.230.102.159:8082/api/v1/cases/mobile_api/10/my-feed/
Response headers	<pre>HTTP/1.1 200 OK Server: nginx/1.14.0 (Ubuntu) Date: Thu, 26 Mar 2020 09:27:51 GMT Content-Type: application/json Content-Length: 3111 Connection: close Vary: Accept, Origin, Cookie</pre>

	Allow: GET, POST, HEAD, OPTIONS X-Frame-Options: SAMEORIGIN
Response body	<pre>[{ "id": 113, "name": "George Vafeiadis", "description": "test task 4", "tag": "task", "is_visible_to_volunteers": false, "image": null, "address": null, "latitude": 38.0409981, "longitude": 23.6868846, "radius": 5.0, "created_at": "2020-03-26T09:09:42.218692Z", "updated_at": "2020-03-26T09:09:42.218728Z", "user": 27, "case": 10 }, { "id": 114, "name": "George Vafeiadis", "description": "test task 5", "tag": "task", "is_visible_to_volunteers": false, "image": null, "address": null, "latitude": 38.0402093, "longitude": 23.6897721, "radius": 5.0, "created_at": "2020-03-26T09:27:45.529238Z", "updated_at": "2020-03-26T09:27:45.529274Z", "user": 27, "case": 10 }]</pre>

Sampler result	<div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px;"> <div style="display: flex; border-bottom: 1px solid #ccc;"> Sampler result Request Response data </div> <pre style="font-family: monospace; font-size: 0.9em; margin-top: 5px;"> Thread Name: Sample Start:2020-03-26 11:27:51 EET Load time:226 Connect Time:72 Latency:225 Size in bytes:3363 Sent bytes:262 Headers size in bytes:252 Body size in bytes:3111 Sample Count:1 Error Count:0 Data type ("text" "bin" ""):text Response code:200 Response message:OK HTTPSampleResult fields: ContentType: application/json DataEncoding: null </pre> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: flex-end; margin-top: 5px;"> Raw Parsed </div> </div>
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Send feed

This request represents the process of providing information to the Network Manager. This information has been sent by the Volunteer.

HTTP Request	Send feedback to Network/Organization Manager
Request headers	<pre style="font-family: monospace; font-size: 0.9em;"> Connection: close Authorization: Bearer {authorization token} Host: 157.230.102.159:8082 Accept-Encoding: gzip Accept: application/json User-Agent: okhttp/3.10.0 Content-Length: 428 Content-Type: multipart/form-data; boundary=kUEMGAMQcGbqhzxcHztyBT1niyEpXG </pre>
Request Body	<pre style="font-family: monospace; font-size: 0.9em;"> POST http://157.230.102.159:8082/api/v1/cases/mobile_api/10/feed/ POST data: --kUEMGAMQcGbqhzxcHztyBT1niyEpXGUE Content-Disposition: form-data; name="longitude" 23.6897721 --kUEMGAMQcGbqhzxcHztyBT1niyEpXGUE Content-Disposition: form-data; name="latitude" </pre>

	<pre> 38.0402093 --kUEMGAMQcGbqhzxcHztyBT1niyEpXGUE Content-Disposition: form-data; name="tag" task --kUEMGAMQcGbqhzxcHztyBT1niyEpXGUE Content-Disposition: form-data; name="description" test task 5 --kUEMGAMQcGbqhzxcHztyBT1niyEpXGUE-- </pre>
Response headers	<pre> HTTP/1.1 201 Created Server: nginx/1.14.0 (Ubuntu) Date: Thu, 26 Mar 2020 09:27:45 GMT Content-Type: application/json Content-Length: 302 Connection: close Vary: Accept, Origin, Cookie Allow: GET, POST, HEAD, OPTIONS X-Frame-Options: SAMEORIGIN </pre>
Response body	<pre> { "id": 114, "name": "George Vafeiadis", "description": "test task 5", "tag": "task", "is_visible_to_volunteers": false, "image": null, "address": null, "latitude": 38.0402093, "longitude": 23.6897721, "radius": 5.0, "created_at": "2020-03-26T09:27:45.529238Z", "updated_at": "2020-03-26T09:27:45.529274Z", "user": 27, "case": 10 } </pre>

Sampler result	<div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; background-color: #333; color: #eee; padding: 10px;"> <div style="display: flex; border-bottom: 1px solid #555; margin-bottom: 5px;"> Sampler result Request Response data </div> <pre style="font-family: monospace; font-size: 0.9em; margin: 0;"> Thread Name: Sample Start:2020-03-26 11:27:45 EET Load time:308 Connect Time:73 Latency:308 Size in bytes:558 Sent bytes:755 Headers size in bytes:256 Body size in bytes:302 Sample Count:1 Error Count:0 Data type ("text" "bin" ""):text Response code:201 Response message:Created HTTPSarResult fields: ContentType: application/json DataEncoding: null </pre> <div style="display: flex; margin-top: 5px;"> Raw Parsed </div> </div>
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Volunteers

This request represents the list of volunteers who are involved in a specific case.

HTTP Request	Get volunteers
Request headers	Connection: close Authorization: Bearer {authorization token} Host: 157.230.102.159:8082 Content-type: application/json Accept-Encoding: gzip Accept: application/json User-Agent: okhttp/3.10.0
Request Body	GET http://157.230.102.159:8082/api/v1/cases/mobile_api/10/volunteers/
Response headers	HTTP/1.1 200 OK Server: nginx/1.14.0 (Ubuntu) Date: Thu, 26 Mar 2020 09:27:46 GMT Content-Type: application/json Content-Length: 843 Connection: close Vary: Accept, Origin, Cookie Allow: GET, POST, HEAD, OPTIONS X-Frame-Options: SAMEORIGIN

Response body	<pre>[{ "id": 18, "image": "http://157.230.102.159:8082/media/cases/10/GRPAKCFL8L8VZHFWONDKLN5K5SXH4T XX.jpg", "child_name": "test name", "is_amber_alert": false, "first_name": "George", "last_name": "Vafeiadis", "email": "giovaf@test.com", "has_accept_invitation": true, "is_team_leader": true, "team_name": "The A team", "created_at": "2020-01-13T15:03:30.917377Z", "updated_at": "2020-01-13T15:09:57.517277Z", "case": 10, "user": 27 }, { "id": 20, "image": "http://157.230.102.159:8082/media/cases/10/GRPAKCFL8L8VZHFWONDKLN5K5SXH4T XX.jpg", "child_name": "test name", "is_amber_alert": false, "first_name": "george", "last_name": "vafeiadis", "email": "vaf@test.com", "has_accept_invitation": true, "is_team_leader": false, "team_name": null, "created_at": "2020-02-13T15:12:18.804140Z", "updated_at": "2020-02-13T16:24:32.532835Z", "case": 10, "user": 34 }]</pre>
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Follow case

This request represents cases which are followed by the user and for which the user receives notifications whether they are within the alert radius or not.

HTTP Request	GET Cases which are followed by the user
Request headers	<p>Connection: close</p> <p>Authorization: Bearer {authorization token}</p> <p>Host: 157.230.102.159:8082</p> <p>Content-type: application/json</p> <p>Accept-Encoding: gzip</p> <p>Accept: application/json</p> <p>User-Agent: okhttp/3.10.0</p>
Request Body	GET http://157.230.102.159:8082/api/v1/cases/mobile_api/followed-cases/
Response headers	<p>HTTP/1.1 200 OK</p> <p>Server: nginx/1.14.0 (Ubuntu)</p> <p>Date: Thu, 26 Mar 2020 09:28:00 GMT</p> <p>Content-Type: application/json</p> <p>Content-Length: 1962</p> <p>Connection: close</p> <p>Vary: Accept, Origin, Cookie</p> <p>Allow: GET, HEAD, OPTIONS</p> <p>X-Frame-Options: SAMEORIGIN</p>

Response body	<pre>[{ "id": 10, "disappearance_date": "2019-12-15T20:50:00.443000Z", "disappearance_location": "ermou athens", "arrival_date": null, "first_name": "test", "last_name": "name", "father_fullname": null, "mother_fullname": null, "gender": null, "phone": null, "date_of_birth": null, "current_facility_id": null, "current_facility": null, "data": null, "custom_name": "Test2 T.", "blockchain_address": null, "presence_status": "present", "status": "active", "arrival_at_facility_date": null, "end_date": null, "created_at": "2019-12-16T10:06:07.300665Z", "updated_at": "2020-03-19T20:53:29.450022Z", "description": null, "default_message": null, "profile_photo": "http://157.230.102.159:8082/media/cases/10/GRPAKCFL8L8VZHFWONDKLN5K5SX H4TXX.jpg", "has_mobile_phone": null, "has_money_or_credit": null, "has_area_knowledge": null, "clothing_with_scent": null, "rescue_teams_utilized": false, "volunteers_utilized": false, "transit_country": null, "disappearance_type": null, "amber_alert": false, "eye_color": null, "hair_color": null, "skin_color": null, "height": null, "weight": null, "stature": null, "body_type": null,</pre>
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	<pre>"haircut": null, "characteristics": null, "home_address": null, "home_country": null, "home_postal_code": null, "birth_country": null, "education_level": null, "languages_spoken": null, "nationality": null, "addiction": null, "health_issues": null, "medical_treatment_required": null, "health_issues_description": null, "triggered_event": null, "concerns": null, "mental_disorders": null, "psychological_disorders": null, "physical_disabilities": null, "living_environment": null, "family_members": null, "school_grades": null, "hobbies": null, "relationship_status": null, "religion": null, "disappearance_reasons": null, "parents_profile": null, "is_high_risk": null, "is_first_time_missing": null, "has_trafficking_history": null, "is_refugee": null, "legal_status": null, "contacted_date": null, "risk_indicator": 0.0, "days_diff": 0.0, "go_missing_possibility": 0.0, "current_mindset": null, "organization": 1, "child": 11, "owner": null, "facility": [], "user": [26, 34, 27] }]</pre>
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Sampler result	<div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px;"> <div style="display: flex; border-bottom: 1px solid #ccc;"> Sampler result Request Response data </div> <pre style="font-family: monospace; font-size: 0.9em; margin-top: 5px;"> Thread Name: Sample Start:2020-03-26 11:28:00 EET Load time:236 Connect Time:72 Latency:236 Size in bytes:2208 Sent bytes:266 Headers size in bytes:246 Body size in bytes:1962 Sample Count:1 Error Count:0 Data type ("text" "bin" ""):text Response code:200 Response message:OK HTTPSampleResult fields: ContentType: application/json DataEncoding: null </pre> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: flex-end; margin-top: 5px;"> Raw Parsed </div> </div>
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Logout

This request represents the logout activity of an authenticated volunteer user.

HTTP Request	Logout from the app
Request headers	<pre style="font-family: monospace; font-size: 0.9em; margin: 0;"> Connection: close Authorization: Bearer {authorization token} Host: 157.230.102.159:8082 Content-Type: application/x-www-form-urlencoded Accept-Encoding: gzip Accept: application/json User-Agent: okhttp/3.10.0 Content-Length: 56 </pre>
Request Body	<pre style="font-family: monospace; font-size: 0.9em; margin: 0;"> POST http://157.230.102.159:8082/api/v1/users/mobile_api/logout/ POST data: uuid={uuid} </pre>
Response headers	<pre style="font-family: monospace; font-size: 0.9em; margin: 0;"> HTTP/1.1 204 No Content Server: nginx/1.14.0 (Ubuntu) Date: Thu, 26 Mar 2020 09:28:11 GMT Content-Length: 0 Connection: close Vary: Accept, Origin, Cookie </pre>

	<p>Allow: POST, OPTIONS X-Frame-Options: SAMEORIGIN</p>
<p>Response body</p>	<p>No response body available</p>
<p>Sampler result</p>	<pre> Sampler result Request Response data Thread Name: Sample Start:2020-03-26 11:28:11 EET Load time:275 Connect Time:72 Latency:0 Size in bytes:214 Sent bytes:352 Headers size in bytes:214 Body size in bytes:0 Sample Count:1 Error Count:0 Data type ("text" "bin" "): Response code:204 Response message:No Content HTTPSampleResult fields: ContentType: DataEncoding: null Raw Parsed </pre>